

Deliverable 5.4

Design and Specification of the WP5 final ERL Smart City Competition

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List of acronyms

SciRoc	Smart Cities Robotics Challenge
ERL	European Robotic League

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1. Introduction

SciRoc is an EU-H2020 funded project supporting the European Robotics League (ERL). Prior to 2018, the ERL, funded by the European Commission to advance research, development and innovation in robotics and artificial intelligence, has run in three categories: Consumer, Emergency and Professional Service Robots. Now teams from all three categories meet every two years (i.e., in years 2019 and 2021) in the ERL Smart Cities Robotics Challenge (SciRoc), which aims to demonstrate how real robots can make our lives better in urban environments. The second SCIROC event is set to take place in Bologna, Italy, 6-11 September. We recall that the choice of Bologna was the result of an open call, through which Bologna was selected among several competing candidate cities (see Del. 5.3). After the selection, there have been several meetings in the fall 2020 to decide whether to postpone the event to 2022, possibly in conjunction with IJCAI 2022, or keep the original schedule that planned the event in September 2021. After a careful evaluation of pros and cons and after having acquired the indications from Bologna, it was decided to keep the original schedule. However, the development of the pandemics impacted negatively on the preparation of the event, since the uncertainty of the situation makes it difficult to recruit teams, sponsors and supporting institutions on site. In order to mitigate the uncertainties deriving from the pandemics, we have started the design of the competition trying to accommodate the possibility of a remote event, or, more precisely, of supporting the remote participation of teams. It is worth emphasizing that this is an unprecedented technical and organizational challenge, since there are no examples neither in the realm of robotic competitions nor in other application settings of code developed remotely that is executed on a real robot elsewhere. Largely due to this difficulty, we notice that major robotic competitions (e.g. RoboCup) have postponed their next event to 2022. The SciRoc consortium has been working hard to implement the concept of remote participation of teams and found an excellent support form PAL Robotics. PAL decided to continue and reinforce the collaboration with SciRoc, embracing the idea of supporting the creation of a software framework for remote participation and providing a TIAGo and, hopefully, a Rheem-c robot on site to run the software developed by remote participants. The support from PAL Robotics is the first key input to the design of the episodes for the 2nd SciRoc challenge. The second input came from the organizing city, Bologna, which chose the theme of 'Smart Inclusion'.

As with our first SciRoc event, the competition will be structured into a series of **episodes** and in order to start the design process, we have initially brainstormed on the possible innovations to be introduced in the episodes to implement the smart inclusion concept.

As a result, we came up with a list of five episodes that compromise between the need to keep a large coverage of the previous ones (to leverage the expertise acquired by the teams that

participated in the 1st SciRoc challenge), and the goal to introduce the theme suggested by the organizing city. Consequently, we formed five working groups, which developed a description of the following episodes:

- Coffee shop (Episode 1),
- Sign language (episode 2),
- Shopping cart (episode 3),
- Emergency (episode 4)
- Pick and pack (episode 5),

each consisting of a task to be performed through addressing specific research challenges. A brief overview of the episodes, highlighting the key ideas is provided below.

Episode 1 is a remake of the Coffee Shop episode from the first SciRoc Challenge, but with the important addition of the framework for remote participation and the availability of a simulation environment.

Episode 2 is the one that has been specifically designed in response to a specific case for inclusion pointed out by the organizing city: the sign language for mute deaf people. The initial suggestion was to add the communication through sign language in the Coffee Shop episode. Later, it was decided to handle it also as a separate episode in order to enable for the participation of teams with a specific expertise on sign language, but little background in robotics. We are in the process of building a novel data set with videos reproducing a restricted language for the interaction in a coffee shop.

Episode 3 builds on the collaboration with the Eurobench project. This collaboration led to the “Open the door” episode in the 1st SciRoc challenge and, according to the original plan, it is based on the “Pushing the cart” benchmark of Eurobench. The challenge also provides a simulation environment and supports the possibility of remote participation.

Episode 4 takes inspiration from the pandemics and tries to address the need to quickly transport medicines next to a patient through a robot (initially a small drone, later replaced by ground robot). Unfortunately, this seems more than anything else reflecting the atmosphere of the present pandemic world.

Episode 5 is a continuation of the liason established in the first SciRoc challenge with Ocado. The theme is again the manipulation of shopping items on the shelves of a large store, with an industrially driven implementation. A distributed execution of the challenge has also been addressed.

At the time of writing the rulebooks are being finalized while the actual setup of the episodes in the city of Bologna is under negotiation. Obviously, due to the current pandemic situation, all our proposed activities will be implemented in compliance with local regulations and safety procedures that will be in place in Bologna at the time of the competition.

It is our aim and our hope that the second SCIROC event will be physically implemented and also be attended by the teams in person, in Bologna. However, it is worth emphasizing that our design of the competition is trying to accommodate also for a scenario where physical implementation must comply with distancing restrictions and, regrettably, remote attendance. The rulebooks will appear in the Appendix of this deliverable, while some notes on the implementation will be reported in Del 5.5, to be released after the event.

2. Episode definitions

Episode 1 Coffee shop

In this episode the robot will assist the staff of a coffee shop to take care of their customers. The robot is required to recognise and report the status of all tables inside the shop, to take orders from customers and to deliver objects to and from the customers' tables.

The main functionalities that are evaluated in this episode are **people perception** and **object perception**. Moreover, in connection with Episode 2, we will address also the **interaction through sign language**. The latter will be considered as an option that would have an impact on the score, but is not mandatory. It is worth mentioning that the robot should have other functionalities (although not explicitly targeted in the score) including navigation, speech synthesis, spoken language.

This episode can be entered in a Gazebo simulator modality or with actual robots. Moreover, the teams will be allowed to participate in the competition both remotely and onsite. Notice that remote participation is possible also on real robots, since a TIAGO robot will be available to run the code provided by remote participants.

The sign language component is not available in the simulated scenario, but it will be included on the real robot version, as an option to increase the overall score.

Notes: 1) No manipulation actions are required, the objects are placed and gathered by people to and from the tray on the robot. 2) Objects to deliver are such that they will fit on the robot tray.

Simulation Version

The Simulation version of this episode can be used by teams who are unable to travel to the event due to COVID related restrictions. All other teams should participate at the physical event in Bologna using the Real Robot version (outlined below).

The goal of the simulation environment is to allow for the development of the whole architecture, main functionalities as Person and Object perception are simplified by the simulation set up. Other functionalities needed are navigation and, optionally, Spoken Language to interact with customers. In the case of Spoken Language the Spoken Language interpretation is up to the team, while the text-to-speech is provided by the TIAGO voice. The simulation environment can be regarded as a starting basis for the development of the real robot system.

Platform allowed

The simulation environment will be in Gazebo, where a model of the TIAGO robot and a model of the coffee shop environment are available. The robot is equipped with a tray for transporting a few small objects, and sensors for people/object perception and navigation in the virtual environment. All the sensors available on the TIAGO are accessible in the simulation environment (except for the microphone, which is handled through the computer microphone).

Set up

A virtual coffee shop (e.g. 5 meters * 9 meters), with a few tables and typical objects (e.g. coffee cups, napkins, ...) will be made available resembling the real competition arena to be made available in Bologna. The environment will consist of people waiting to be served, customers already served, tables that need to be cleaned, and empty tables ready to receive new customers (see Fig. 1 Coffee Shop Scenario in Gazebo).

Fig. 1 Coffee Shop Scenario in Gazebo

Procedure

The robot is placed in a starting location near the counter and the trial begins. The robot will need to navigate around the shop and assess the status of all tables. If a table is clean but with customers present at the table, the robot will accept an order from that table and will report it to the kitchen. The interaction with customers can be via written text (or via spoken language with a higher score).

The robot will then navigate to the counter to collect and deliver the objects to that table. The robot does not require manipulation. Hence the object will be taken by the customers from the robot tray. The order provided by the counter will have one of the items missing or incorrect and the robot must identify and correct the mistake. A run terminates when the robot has delivered the order to the table. A time limit will conclude the episode if the robot gets stuck.

Scoring

Evaluation of the performance of a robot is based on the concept of performance classes employed in the ERL competitions. The performance class of a robot is determined by the number of achievements (or goals) that the robot collects during its execution of the assigned task. Within each class, ranking is defined according to the number of penalties collected by the robots belonging to the class. Examples of Achievements and Penalties for this episode is as follows:

Achievements

- The robot correctly reports all the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers at every table.
- The robot reaches an unserved table and asks the order.
- The robot correctly understands and communicates the order of the customer to the counter.
- The robot correctly recognises the wrong or missing item and requests correction of the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.

Penalising behaviours

- The robot hits any of the furniture or objects (one penalty for each hit).
- The robot requires multiple repetition of the speech command / The robot requires multiple repetition of a customer speech act.

Disqualifying behaviours

- The robot hits a human.

Real Robot Version

The real robot version of the episode will require all the functionalities as specified in the general description.

Platform allowed

A mobile service robot that is equipped with a tray, a planar surface or any other way of transporting a few small objects is required. The robot must be equipped with sensors for people/object perception and navigation. The optional human-robot interaction based on sign language will require 1 arm and a hand.

A TIAGO robot will be provided on site to support remote participation of teams without a robot (see Fig. 2). The remote participation will be implemented through the delivery of a docker that will be installed and run on site. Details on the actual procedure will be provided in the full rulebook.

Fig. 2 One Arm TIAGO Robot with the detail of the hey5 hand

Set up

A coffee shop like arena (e.g. 5 meters * 9 meters), with a few tables and typical objects (e.g. coffee cups, napkins, ...) will be made available. Objects will be a fixed set, to be disclosed only at the competition site.

The environment will be populated by a set of people waiting to be served, customers already served, tables that need to be cleaned, and some cleaned tables, empty tables ready for new customers.

Deaf-mute customers will be present for the teams that implement the sign language option.

Procedure

The robot is placed in a starting location near the counter and the trial begins. The robot is required to navigate around the shop and assess the status of all the tables. If a table is clean, but with customers present at the table, the robot will accept an order from that table and will report it to the counter. The interaction with customers can be via spoken language or through sign language for deaf people (with a higher score).

The robot will then navigate to the counter to collect and remember the order and will deliver the objects to that table. The order provided by the counter will have one of the items missing or incorrect and the robot must identify and correct the mistake.

Scoring

Evaluation of the performance of a robot is based on the concept of performance classes employed in the ERL competitions. The performance class of a robot is determined by the number of achievements (or goals) that the robot collects during its execution of the assigned task. Within each class, ranking is defined according to the number of penalties collected by the robots belonging to the class. Examples of Achievements and Penalties for this episode is as follows:

Achievements

- The robot correctly reports all the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers for all tables with customers.
- The robot reaches an unserved table and asks for the order.
- The robot uses sign language to greet and take the order of a deaf-mute person
- The robot correctly understands and informs the order of the customer to the counter.
- The robot correctly understands and informs the order of the deaf-mute customer to the counter.
- The robot correctly recognises the wrong or missing item and corrects the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.

Penalising behaviours

- The robot requires multiple repetition of the speech command / The robot requires multiple repetition of the sign language from deaf person.
- The robot hits any of the furniture or objects (one penalty for each hit).

Disqualifying behaviours

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot damages the furniture and/or objects.

Episode 2 Sign language

A specific challenge for the robot operating in a coffee shop that we aim to explore is the interaction through sign languages developed by and for deaf people. The world of sign language is quite complex and there are many sign languages: being that the competition is hosted in Italy, the chosen variant is the Italian one. However, the full sign language would be out of reach; therefore, a suitable subset of the Italian Sign Language (LIS) will be devised that can support the basic interaction in the coffee shop and that can be handled by a TIAGo robot with a single arm and the hand (or any other platform with similar functionalities).

The interaction through LIS is addressed specifically by Episode 2, but it will be also an addition to the Coffee Shop Episode 1 (namely teams may implement the interaction using LIS for the Coffee Shop Episode to gain a better score). In this way, teams can enter the competition in Episode 2, focusing on the sign language only, without requiring the implementation of all the functionalities required for Episode 1.

The challenge is naturally split according to the two directions of the communication flow: the robot interpreting the sign language by humans (LIS comprehension) and the robot “speaking” in sign language (LIS production).

Platforms allowed

Thanks to the support by PAL Robotics a TIAGo robot equipped with one arm and the hand will be available to support both on site and remote participation (see Fig.2). Any mobile basis with one arm with a hand would be allowed to enter the competition.

Set up

The subset of the sign language to be used in the competition is currently being defined. We are considering 20 signs and 10 phrases. Signs will be defined both for specific items to be ordered at the coffee shop and for simple sentences that support the interaction. The language definition will be delivered together with a set of videos, where the signs are played by experts, for example: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5CSdGzDgSwY>

For the sign language comprehension experts will be placed in front of the robot and the robot should classify the signs or the phrases played by the experts. Multiple rounds will be arranged with the support of multiple experts.

For the sign language production the robot will be asked to play several signs and a set of 3 experts acting as referees will evaluate the correctness and the quality of the execution, according to a pre-defined evaluation form.

Procedure

According to the given description the procedure is split in two parts:

Task 1 Interpretation: The robot is placed in front of the expert; the robot should comprehend the sign language played by the expert. In each run the expert will play a series of signs/phrases. Each team will be faced with the same set of experts through repeated runs. There will be an increasing level of difficulty in the comprehension, ranging from single signs, to sequences of two signs and phrases with more than two signs.

Task 2 Generation: The robot is placed in front of the expert referees, and will be given a list of signs/phrases to be played. Also in the production task there will be an increasing level of difficulty, ranging from single signs, to sequences of two signs and phrases with more than two signs.

The challenge will run on 3 days, 2 days of preliminaries and one day of finals. The number of runs for both tasks in each day will be defined based on the number of participating teams.

Since this episode is focused on two specific functionalities the evaluation of the performance will be based on the following measures:

- The number of correctly interpreted signs.
- The score achieved in the execution of sign language instances, which is based both on quantitative and on qualitative criteria.

Episode 3 Shopping cart

Episode 3 aims at evaluating the capability of a robot to interact with one challenging device found in environments designed for humans: the shopping cart.

Episode 3 is a joint effort between European projects SciRoc and Eurobench. Episode 3 corresponds in fact to the BEAST (Benchmark-Enabling Active Shopping Trolley) Eurobench benchmark for mobile robots.

The physical elements of the Episode are its testbed. The BEAST testbed comprises two main elements:

- the arena, i.e. the passive structured environment where the Episode takes place;
- the active shopping cart, i.e. a robotised shopping cart capable of behaviours which include, but are not limited to, those of a standard cart.

The aim of the BEAST benchmark is to evaluate the capability of a mobile robot to correctly manoeuvre a wheeled device (shopping cart or walker). In this context, “correctly manoeuvre” involves performance metrics concerning geometry (such as staying close to a predefined trajectory or maximising distance from obstacles), time, force (e.g., smooth application of force to the handle over time instead of abrupt bursts). The BEAST benchmark makes use of the capability of the active element (cart or walker) of the testbed to simulate physical disturbances that occur in real-world scenarios, such as ly distributed wheel friction or small obstacles on the ground (such as a low step or a pebble).

Platforms Allowed

The BEAST benchmark is suitable for any autonomous mobile agent that is physically capable of operating the active trolley or walker in the arena. As such, it can be executed by any robot provided with an end-effector(s) suitable for interaction with the active cart’s handle, including (but not limited to) humanoid robots. Execution of the benchmark by humans, while not explicitly considered, is nonetheless fully possible: thus making it possible to collect “human baseline” datasets to be compared with those generated by robots.

Setup

The setup is composed of an arena and an active (i.e., robotised) cart, plus a few additional pieces of equipment for network and processing. Setup is simplified and even if performed from scratch (with the arena broken down to its components) should not take more than a workday for an experienced operator.

Since the shopping cart is not designed to be disassembled, the only piece of the testbed that requires physical assembling is the arena. The walls of the arena are composed of 1 m tall panels.

The arena includes two apertures. One of them goes down to the ground, and is used for entry and exit; the other is a cutout in the surrounding wall. The orange pillars in the rendering are heavy PVC tubes for construction, while the white panels composing the walls of the arena are made of low-density PVC, similar to the commercial product called Forex. Structural support is provided to the arena by a rigid frame built from modular aluminium profiles with a 40 x 40 mm square cross section. Profile elements include an 8 mm wide groove, used both to insert mechanical joints (e.g, those that connect the profiles, described below) and to guide and contain the edge of the wall elements. In order to accommodate possible unevenness of the floor over the (quite extensive) perimeter of the arena, the whole structure is supported by adjustable feet. Below (see Fig.3) are images of the arena and of the active shopping cart.

Fig. 3 Competition arena and the shopping cart

Procedure

While executing the benchmark, the shopping cart (pushed by the robot) has to follow the trajectory (see Fig. 4). Such trajectory is composed of four parts:

- A first section where the cart should proceed along a straight line;
- A second section where the cart is required to invert its direction of motion by going around a pillar (no specification are given on trajectory shape here: however, if planning is

not done correctly -considering the differential drive kinematics of the front wheels of the trolley- the execution of this part of the benchmark can easily require backtracking);

- A third section that requires that the cart passes between the same couple of pillars where the first section had its start, but in the opposite direction (no constraints are given to trajectory shape except that the cart must pass between the pillars);
- A fourth section where the cart needs to be “parked” in the corner of the test bed.

Fig. 4 Trajectory in episode 3

More specifically, the phases of the protocol of the Episode are defined with respect to the numbered Checkpoints (line segments, see Fig. 5). Such phases are:

- The trolley is positioned in the start pose, where the central point between its front wheels (i.e., the actuated ones) is in the centre of Checkpoint 1. This phase is human-executed and not part of the benchmark. The robot is positioned inside the area of the test bed, between the trolley and the entrance to the test bed, in front of the centre point of the trolley's handle, at a sufficient distance from it that in order to reach the handle the robot has to move its whole body with respect to the ground. The referees are in charge of defining such distance.

- The benchmark is started.
- The robot has to grasp the trolley's handle. The robot can optionally start with its end effectors already positioned on the handle. In that case this step is human-executed before the start of the benchmark (step 2).
- The robot has to navigate, while pushing the trolley, through all checkpoints in the correct order (from 1 to 5).
- The benchmark reaches its completion: this happens in three cases (see section “Scoring” for details): (i) the benchmark gets manually interrupted by the referees (e.g., because the robot executed a Disqualifying Behaviour); (ii) the robot collected the Achievement A6; (iii) the benchmark's timeout has been reached.

Fig. 5 Numbered checkpoints (line segments)

Simulated Episode Competition

The simulation environment is built using the Gazebo simulator and ROS framework.

Participants will access the simulated robot (both to read sensor observation and command the robot actuators) by coding a ROS node wrapper that connects their approach to the Gazebo plugin of the robot. Furthermore, the simulated episode suite will be released with a docker image that can be easily executed. The docker image will deliver all the features described in the Setup section, and it will configure the sensor data flow on the same channels of the real-robot onsite scenario (e.g. ROS topics, data format). Such a setup allows to transparently and interchangeably switch between the real and simulated execution of the episode which is mandatory to preserve the robotic task as described in the Procedure section; and the bench marking system described in the Scoring section.

The figure 6 shows the simulated environment running in a docker container. The blue shaded area is the laser sensor visualisation while on the bottom-right corner the robot camera stream. In this scenario, the simulated PAL robot Reem-C is operated by relying upon the dedicated Gazebo plugin released by the robot manufacturer.

Fig. 6 Simulated environment running in a docker container

Scoring

The scoring mechanism for this Episode complies with the framework used by the European Robotics League for Task Benchmarks. As such, it is based on the three sets of Achievements, Penalising Behaviours and Disqualifying Behaviours described in the following.

Achievements

A1 The robot has autonomously grasped the trolley's handle, without any human intervention.

A2 The trolley has reached Checkpoint 1. The trajectory of the trolley during this part of the benchmark should be as close to parallel to the side wall as possible. Assessment of deviations does not affect the Achievements, but will be used to break ties.

A3 The trolley has reached Checkpoint 2.

A4 The trolley has reached Checkpoint 3.

A5 The trolley has reached Checkpoint 4.

A6 The trolley has reached Checkpoint 5.

Achievements can be collected only in the specified order.

Achievements A2...A6 require that the trolley, pushed by the robot, reaches specific checkpoints. The definition of “Reaching a checkpoint” is the following:

The trolley reaches a checkpoint when the projection on the floor of the central point between its two front wheels (i.e., the actuated wheels) crosses the line segment corresponding to the checkpoint, without having crossed any other checkpoints before.

Let CP be the checkpoint that an Achievement is associated to. If the trolley reaches any checkpoint different from CP before it reaches CP, the benchmark gets interrupted by the referees and no further Achievements can be collected.

When the execution of the benchmark gets interrupted in this way, the duration of its execution is conventionally set to the full allowed duration up to the timeout (this is done to avoid unfair advantage to robots that provoke an interruption, since execution time is used to break ties).

For Achievements A2...A6 no constraints are imposed to trajectory shape beyond those imposed by the definition of “reaching a checkpoint”.

Penalising Behaviours

PB1 – The robot hits any piece of the benchmark setup (e.g., a part of the door assembly) without inflicting damage. An exception is made for the elements of the shopping cart, which can be hit without penalty (provided that they do not get damaged).

PB2 – The robot falls down and requires that the robot’s team performs a manual get-up.

For the definition of the Penalising Behaviours (and, later, of the Disqualifying Behaviours) the following definitions of “damage” and “hit” are used:

A damage is any geometric change that does not revert spontaneously within 10 seconds, even if the change would be reversible through suitable intervention (e.g., a wall panel is pushed out of its normal position)

A hit is a physical contact event where the robot applies forces sufficient to cause damage (even if no damage occurs): referees are in charge of deciding what physical contacts must be classified as hits.

An additional penalising behaviour is inflicted to the team every time the corresponding event occurs, even if the team has already been penalised for the very same behaviour.

Disqualifying Behaviours

DB1 – The robot hits a human (e.g., a referee).

DB2 – The robot damages any piece of the benchmark setup.

DB3 – The robot exits the test bed area ¹.

DB4 – The trolley moves for a duration of 5 s or more while the robot is continuously in contact with any part of it different from the handle, OR the overall time that the trolley moves while the robot is in contact with any part of it different from the handle is over 30 s.

Ties

It may happen that two robots get the exact same number of Achievements and the exact same number of Penalising Behaviours, without incurring into any Disqualifying Behaviours. In this case, to avoid ties, the following criteria is applied: tie-breaking criterion: the performance of the robot which finished the benchmark in a shorter time is considered as better.

¹ The robot is considered as outside the testbed area when none of its elements has a projection on the floor that lies inside the 3 m by 6 m rectangular area of the floor which contains the testbed

Episode 4 Emergency

Delivery of medicines to isolated persons and accompany them to medical centre. A medicine is ordered by a person in Bologna that cannot go out (due to quarantine related issues or because the person is disabled). The robot must be able to move autonomously to the location where the citizen is waiting. The robot might need to detect and avoid possible obstacles on the way (static and dynamic), and it must consider that GPS coverage is not always guaranteed. Once the robot arrives to the citizen, the robot should interact with him (in English) to deliver the proper medicine and inform about the needed dosage. Depending on the person health, it could be also possible that the robot should accompany the person to the nearest medical centre to see a doctor.

Platforms Allowed

Ground robots that can carry items to specific locations, navigate in outdoor (and maybe indoor spaces), detect and avoid obstacles (dynamic and static), have incorporated basic human-robot interaction with the citizens. Specific limitations may be applied to large ground robots for safety reasons. Apart from this, any ground robot platform will be able to enter the competition for this episode.

Set up

The episode must take place in an urban area of Bologna. Within this urban area there should be two identified locations: medical centre (starting point of the robot) and the location where the medicine has to be delivered (where the citizen is). Also, fixed (and mobile) obstacles could be included within this area. Depending on the specific area, dead ends and indoor spaces could be used to incorporate more realism to the episode.

Procedure

According to the given description the procedure is split in two parts.

Task 1 (Delivery of medicine): a medicine request reaches a pharmacy in downtown Bologna. The responsibility of the pharmacy attaches the medicine to the ground robot. The robot goes with the medicine towards the location, detecting and avoiding different obstacles on the way (including other pedestrians). Once at the location, it must enter through an opening (size TBD), detect the person, stop nearby (accuracy requirement TBD) and interact with the person to confirm his/her identity, deliver the proper medicine and inform about the required dosage. There will be an increasing level of difficulty in the types and number of obstacles that the robot can encounter.

Task 2 (Accompany to medical centre): In case the person does not feel well and it is not enough with the medicine, the robot should ask the citizen to accompany him/her to the nearest medical centre. Then, the robot will accompany, side by side, the citizen until they arrive to the medical centre, overcoming dynamic and static obstacles on the way. There will be an increasing level of difficulty in the types and number of obstacles that the robot can encounter.

The challenge will run on 3 days, 2 days of preliminaries and one day of finals. The number of runs for both tasks in each day will be defined based on the number of participating teams.

Episode 5 Pick and Pack

This episode addresses the problem of picking products from a storage container and placing them on a designated shelf. The chosen domain is the operation of an autonomous shop, where the robot helps to manage the inventory of a shop and to organise newly arrived products.

Platforms allowed

Tasks must be completed using a fully autonomous robotic platform with mobile manipulation and perception capabilities (e.g. KUKA YouBot, TIAGO, etc.). In particular, the robot must be able to navigate autonomously in the environment to reach the products inside a storage container or to place items on a shelf. In addition, the robot must be able to detect, grasp and manipulate products in order to deliver them to the designated location. Moreover, the robot should be easily moved in and out of the competition zone, even when not in function, by maximum two team members with minimum effort.

Set up

The episode takes place in an area reproducing a grocery shop. The shop is built with a picking area with a storage container and shelves where products need to be placed.

Procedure

The episode will include one container that will be placed on a fixed location. The Container will contain all the objects that need to be stacked on the shelf. The robot has to pick objects one-by-one from the container and place them on the shelf. A product is considered as delivered only when it is placed on the designated shelf without being in contact with any part of the robot, and the robot has announced its delivery.

Contingency plan for remote competition

In case of a travel ban, the competition will be conducted in remote setup with teams executing the competition in their labs and live streaming the video. The organisers will ship the arena components and the objects to the individual teams. The shelf used for placing the objects will be replaced with additional storage containers. The episode will be modified to pick from one container and place in another container as per the category.

3. Conclusion

The goal of this deliverable is to define the specification of the episodes for the 2nd SciRoc Challenge. To this end, we designed guidelines for each episode which include platforms, procedures, setups, etc. All episodes' offer teams the ability to participate in person or remotely, in case travel to Bologna is not permitted. Full rulebooks containing a detailed description for each episode will be released shortly and included as Appendix.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank PAL Robotics for their support in the definition of the episodes. In particular, Daniel Lopez Puig has supported the implementation of the solution for the remote participation in episode 1, and provided general advice on the definition of the rulebooks of Episode 1 and 2.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Episode 01: Coffee Shop Rulebook

Appendix 2: Episode 02: Sign Language Rulebook

Appendix 3: Episode 03: Shopping Cart Rulebook

Appendix 4: Episode 04: Delivery of Emergency Medicines Rulebook

Appendix 5: Episode 05: Shopping Pick & Pack Rulebook

SCIROC 2021

Episode 01: Coffee shop

Rulebook

Technical Committee

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** All the proposed activities must be performed in compliance with local regulations and safety procedures in Bologna, specially those related to COVID-19 limitations. Teams are invited to participate in the competition both remotely or onsite. Notice that remote participation is possible also on real robots, since a TIAGO robot will be available to run the code provided by remote participants.*

1. General Description

In this episode the robot will assist the staff of a coffee shop to take care of their customers. The robot is required to recognize and report the status of all tables inside the shop, to take orders from customers and to deliver objects to and from the customers' tables.

2. Main scientific challenge

This episode aims at benchmarking some of the key functionalities required by an autonomous service robot to operate inside a coffee shop. The main functionality that is evaluated in this episode is **people perception, object perception and sign language interpretation/generation (optional)**. Additional side functionalities are navigation, speech synthesis, spoken language. This episode can be entered in a Gazebo simulator modality (i.e., simulation version) or with actual robots (i.e., real robot version). The sign language component is not available in the simulated scenario, but it will be included on the real robot version, as an option to increase the overall score.

2.1 Simulation version

The goal of the simulation environment is mainly to allow for the development of the whole system architecture. The main functionalities such as Person and Object perception are simplified by the simulation set up. Other functionalities needed are navigation and, optionally, Spoken Language to interact with customers. In the case of Spoken language the Spoken Language interpretation is up to the team, while the text-to-speech is provided by the TIAGO voice. The simulation environment can be regarded as a starting basis for the development of the real robot system,

2.2 Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

The main functionalities of the real robot version are person and object perception and sign language interpretation and generation.

In addition, other functionalities that are needed to execute the episode are Navigation and Spoken Language interaction. .

3. Platforms allowed

3.1 Simulation Version

The simulation environment will be in Gazebo, where a model of the Tiago robot and a model of the coffee shop environment are available. The robot is equipped with a tray for transporting a few small objects, and sensors for people/object perception and navigation in the virtual environment. All the sensors available on the TIAGO are accessible in the simulation environment (except for the microphone, which is handled through the computer microphone).

3.2 Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

A mobile service robot that is equipped with a tray, a planar surface or any other way of transporting few small objects is required. The robot must be equipped with sensors for people/object perception and navigation. The optional human-robot interaction based on sign language will require 1 arm and a hand (see Fig.1). Tiago robots will also be provided on site to support remote participation of teams without a robot.

Fig. 1 One Arm TIAGO Robot with the detail of the hey5 hand

4. Scenario Setup

4.1 Simulation Version

A virtual coffee shop (e.g., 5 meters * 9 meters), with few tables and typical objects (e.g., coffee cups, napkins, ...) will be made available resembling the real competition arena to be made available in Bologna. The detailed description of all objects and their images will be provided to the participating teams before June 2021. The environment will consist of people waiting to be served, customers already served, tables that need to be cleaned, and empty tables ready to receive new customers (see Fig. 2). It will contain a minimum number of 6 tables to accommodate customers and 1 counter for the staff to place and remove objects. Each of the tables will have a unique identification number. For every trial of the episode, an unknown number of customers (between 5-10 customers) are randomly placed at different tables.

Fig. 2 Coffee Shop Scenario in Gazebo

4.2 Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

An arena representing an ordinary coffeeshop, consisting of multiple tables and chairs, will be used. It will contain a minimum number of 6 tables to accommodate customers and 1 counter for the staff to place and remove objects. A minimum area of approximately 45-50 m² is expected for this episode, however, the actual required dimensions might differ based on the size of the furniture used for the episode. The actual number of tables and chairs along with the detailed floor plan and shop dimensions are communicated to the teams before the competition. Each of the tables will have a unique identification number.

Common tableware and merchandise found at ordinary coffee shops will be used as the objects to be perceived and carried by the robots. Objects can contain actual liquid in them such as a cup of coffee or a glass of water. The detailed description of all objects will be provided to the participating teams 3-4 weeks before the competition and the actual objects are provided to the teams during the setup days. A menu will be placed on all the tables for the visiting customers which will contain the list of all items that can be ordered.

For every trial of the episode, an unknown number of volunteers acting as coffee shop customers are randomly seated at different tables. Deaf-mute customers will be present for the teams that implement the sign language option. The volunteers can compose of team members, members of the technical or organization committee or general public upon filling a consent form. The number of people and their locations are randomly generated by the referees with the help of a random generator right before the trial begins.

5. Software configuration for participation with the TIAGo robot

A private gitlab repository will be created and shared with all the participants. The repository will contain a docker image provided by PAL robotics. The repository will also include the instructions related to downloading, running the docker and detailed documentation about the simulation environment and the Tiago robot. A summary of the **topics, services, actions** and **APIs** useful for this challenge will be also provided in the repository. In order to start the docker loaded on this repository, users will need to log in the docker daemon on gitlab.com and then enter their GitLab user and password. For user convenience, some scripts will be published that simplify the launch of a docker with GPU acceleration. Following the steps properly, users will be able to run gazebo, rviz or other graphical applications from within the docker container. To have an idea of how participants will be able to use the development environment out of the box we created a public docker in the [wiki.ros\(section 2\)](#). Once the docker is running in the user machine, a single roslaunch command will be required to open the simulation and have access to all the **topics, services and actions** to fully interact with the TIAGo in simulation. Participants will need to configure by themselves the camera and microphone of their development pc in order to interact with the already provided ros packages from the docker.

5.1 Simulation Version

Participants should send a unique docker image built on top of the provided one. It is optional to provide the source code as **only the installed workspace** sourced with **`$HOME/solution_ws/install/setup.bash`** will be used to test the solution. Participants should wrap their solution in a single launch file. This unique launch file will be used to score the provided development, meaning that the following command **`roslaunch sciroc_episode_1 solution.launch`** should be enough.

A specific ROS Service will be available for this challenge to facilitate the development of the solution regarding simulated objects. This service will be in charge of creating and putting simulated objects on the tray and move objects bidirectional between tray and table.

5.2 Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

The competition site at Bologna will have a TIAGO robot available for the execution of the code for remote participants. The deployment of the code onto the robot will be done by the technical assistants. The selected participants will be requested to send the same code, in case it is not provided in the first case. The real RGBD camera, stereo microphone and speaker of the TIAGo will be used. A rosbag with real information from the real scenario will be provided in order to let participants do a fine tuning of their code before each run of the competition. This rosbag will include information about real camera videos and recorded audios in different tables with different objects on top of the tables and people sitting on the tables.

6. Procedure

A single trial consists of three phases that are executed sequentially without any interruption. A robot can automatically proceed to the next phase at any time if it is unable to execute or fully complete a phase. The robot must announce the start of a new phase and the robot's objective before execution of a task to allow the referee and the audience to better understand its behavior.

Preparations and start of the trial

- The robot is positioned at the starting location, near the counter.
- Several customers are randomly placed at different tables .

- The team will inform the referee the type of HRI modality the robot plans to execute: Speech, Text (only available in simulation version) or Sign language¹ (only available in real-robot version).
- The trial begins at the scheduled time through a start signal to the robot. The start signal can be either a single press of a button or a simple voice command.

Phase 1: Recognizing the shop's status

- The robot starts by navigating around to recognize the status of all the tables at the shop. For every table, the robot must identify and announce through speech the following information:
 - 1) the table's status:
 - a) Needs serving: The table has customers but no objects on the table.
 - b) Already served: The table contains both customers and objects.
 - c) Needs cleaning: The table has objects but no customers.
 - d) Ready: The table is ready to accept new customers, i.e. no objects and no customers.
 - 2) The number of customers at the table, if any.

In addition to speech announcements, the table's status, and number of customers per table must be stored in a text file on the robot. The referee might request the file to be examined after the termination of a trial.

Phase 2: Taking an order from a customer

- The robot approaches one of the tables that is waiting to be served. Alternatively, if the robot was unable to correctly identify the shop's status in Phase 1, it can go to any table with a customer to continue with the next tasks.
- The robot asks the customers of the table to place their orders.
 - Sign language: The robot must use the manipulator and the hand to greet and ask the customer for the order.
 - Speech: The robot uses speech to request the customers to select their items from the menu
- Three items are selected from the menu by the customers of the table and communicated to the robot through speech, text or sign language.
 - Sign language: Three item names are signed by a deaf-mute customer with a small pause in between each sign (available only for real robot version).
 - Speech: Three item names are pronounced by the customer with a small pause in between.

¹ Please refer to the rulebook of Episode 2_Sign Language concerning the rules of sign language interaction modality.

- Text: Three item names are written by the customer via text (available only for simulation version) .

Phase 3: Delivering the order

- Once the order is placed, the robot navigates to the counter and communicates the order through speech to the assistant behind the counter.
- The order is then placed on the counter by the assistant with one of the items missing or being incorrect.
- The robot must identify the wrong/missing item and ask the assistant to correct the item .
- The items are then placed on to the robot's tray by the assistant and the robot must deliver them to the correct table .
- The customers pick the items, and the robot moves back to the default location.

Note: For the simulated version, multiple Ros services are available that allow the spawning of objects on the counter, replacing the incorrect object, moving items on to the tray and moving items to the table.

7. Timing

The maximum allowed time for a single trial is **15 minutes** (both for simulation version and real robot version) . Note that the trial execution time is an important element in this episode and faster solutions are considered to be better in case of ties in the number of achievements.

8. Score

8.1 Simulation Version

Achievements.

- The robot correctly reports all the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers for all tables with customers.
- The robot reaches an unserved table and asks the order.
- The robot correctly understands (through speech) and communicates the order of the customer to the counter.

- The robot correctly recognizes the wrong or missing item and corrects the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.

Penalising behaviors.

- The robot hits any of the furniture or objects (one penalty for each hit).
- The robot requires multiple repetition of the speech command / The robot requires multiple repetition of a customer speech act.

Disqualifying behaviors.

- The robot hits a human.

8.2 Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

Achievements.

- The robot correctly reports all the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers for all tables with customers.
- The robot reaches an unserved table to take the order.
- The robot uses sign language to greet and ask for the order of a deaf-mute person
- The robot correctly understands and informs the order of a customer to the counter. (1 achievement when using speech. 2 achievements when sign language interpretation is used)
- The robot correctly recognizes the wrong or missing item and corrects the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.

Penalising behaviors.

- The robot hits any of the furniture or objects (one penalty for each hit).
- The robot requires multiple repetition of the speech command / The robot requires multiple repetition of the sign language from deaf person

Disqualifying behaviors.

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot damages the furniture and/or objects.

8.3 Overall score

The competition is executed in two independent categories of “Simulation” and “Real Robot” versions and an award is given for each category. The competition consists of two stages: 1) Competition days, 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held on the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the Final. During the Competition Days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for

each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed. Aggregate score of the Competition Days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition Days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of scheduled episodes M, according to the following table:

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the Final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

The policy for tie braking will be:

- average of first n-1 highest scores
- average of next n-1 highest scores after the median (i.e. n-th highest score)

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same.

9. Ethical Issues

Volunteers involved in the episode, to act as customers, will be selected by the referees among team members, members of TC/OC or deaf-mute customers in advance. The customers will be invited to sign a consensus form where they declare to have been informed about the above mentioned information and that they volunteer to participate in the episode.

10. Detailed instructions for referees

10.1 Simulation Version

The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule of the competition. Also they must make sure that images or gazebo models of the objects on the menu are provided to

the teams during the setup days for training purposes. The referees must ask about the preferred method of human-robot interactions for each team (i.e. text, voice) and plan the episode accordingly.

The referees/organizers have to prepare a representation of the arena in Gazebo and assign the IDs of the tables as in the following illustration:

A competition schedule for the competition trials must be prepared in advance. Time slots of 20 minutes (15 minute trials + 5 minutes of preparation and team exchange) is expected for every trial. Each team must be given an equal opportunity to perform multiple trials (minimum 3 to maximum 9 trials based on the time availability and the number of participating teams).

A minimum number of two referees and up to 10 volunteers acting as customers are required for execution of the test. The referees are expected to carefully study the rules and procedure of the benchmark before the competition. The volunteers will be selected from the members of the teams and other interested audience. When using a member of the general public, a consensus form must be given to them prior to the trial. For each trial, referees should try to initialize the scenario before the trial, assign roles to all volunteers, assign a random number of volunteers who participate in the trial.

The referees/organizers must prepare the scenario in advance according to the description provided in the "Procedures" section. At the end of a trial the referees cross check the score with each other, record the execution time on the score sheet, and confirm the score with the team leader of the participating team.

10.2 Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule to ensure an equal access of the arena to the participating teams for the setup days. Also they must make sure that all objects on the menu are provided to the teams during the setup days for training purposes. The referees must check the robots and approve their safety mechanism

before the actual trials of the competition. They should also ask about the preferred method of human-robot interactions for each team (i.e. sign language, voice) and plan the episode accordingly. Once the arena has been built, and before allowing the teams to access the arena, the referees must mark the location of all tables, wall partitions and other furniture to ensure they are placed back on their default locations for the actual trials.

A competition schedule for the competition trials must be prepared in advance. Time slots of 20 minutes (15 minute trials + 5 minutes of preparation and team exchange) is expected for every trial. Each team must be given an equal opportunity to perform multiple trials (minimum 3 to maximum 9 trials based on the time availability and the number of participating teams).

A minimum number of two referees and up to 10 volunteers acting as customers are required for execution of the test. The referees are expected to carefully study the rules and procedure of the benchmark before the competition. The volunteers will be selected from the members of the teams and other interested audience. When using a member of the general public, a consensus form must be given to them prior to the trial. Referees should try to initialize the scenario before the trial and assign roles to all volunteers.

For every trial, the referees must prepare the scenario according to the description provided in the “Procedures” section by distributing a random number of customers (between 5 to 10 customers) and some objects (from the list of possible objects) on the tables. The distribution difficulty among different trials must not vary significantly. For teams opting for sign-language interaction, deaf mute customers will be used. To begin a trial, one of the referees can stand at the counter. He/she has the responsibility of starting and stopping the benchmark, keeping track of the time and placing and removing the objects from the counter. The second referee will always maintain a distance behind the robot, ensuring the safe operation of the robot at all times and scoring the achievements and penalties using the provided score sheets.

At the end of a trial the referees cross check the score with each other, record the execution time on the score sheet, and confirm the score with the team leader of the participating team.

11. Detailed instructions for teams

11.1 Simulation Version

Teams need to provide the container to the organizers/referees before each trial and they have to provide instructions to execute it. The ros nodes inside the container have to be runnable with a single launch file that controls all the robot's functionalities. The instructions have to contain also a specification of the interaction modality (speech or text) between the robot and the customers. In case of interaction through text, the channel to acquire the order from the customer is represented by the ros Log messages.

The interaction with the ordered objects in the gazebo scene can only happen through four provided ros services:

- *GetThreeOrderedItems.srv* that spawns the requested objects (that are provided through three strings in the call of the service) on the counter of the scene;
- *ChangeTheItem.srv* that allows to change one of the three spawned objects, specifying the name of the one that has to be changed and the replacement
- *MoveItemsOnTheTray.srv* that allows to move all the three objects from the counters to the robot's tray.
- *MoveItemsOnClosestTable.srv* used to move the objects on the robot's closest table.

It is worth noting that all the move services are effective only if the robot is close to the counter or to the destination table within 1.5 meters.

The complete list of objects will be available soon with images and descriptions of objects.

11.2 Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

Teams need to communicate to the organizers all the required information for operating the robot. For example, how should the referee start the robot, what are the preferred methods for human-robot interaction, how to speak/interact with the robot and where/how to place objects on the robot. Teams not using the Tiago robot must show the safety mechanisms of their robots and to demonstrate their use once before the competition begins.

During the competition, teams must prepare their robots outside the arena and can only enter the arena at the assigned times. They must follow the schedule of the trial and comply with the timings described in the "Timing" section. Once the referee signals the end of the trial, the participating team must immediately remove the robot from the arena to allow the next team to enter.

Teams are kindly requested to log and store the robot's Internal data for every trial and to provide it to the organizers after the end of trials. This data will not be used during the competition, but it is used to produce and publish datasets for the benefit of the robotics community. This data must be expressed in the reference frame of the test bed which will be clearly marked on it. There are no restrictions about the framerate and data can be saved at the rate they are acquired or produced. Only data relevant to the episode is expected to be logged and can be in the format of rosbag, in particular the following data is expected to be logged:

1. Images processed for object perception and the calibration info for the images
2. point cloud used to recognize an object
3. The audio signals of the conversation with the customers/staff.
4. The 2D robot pose at the floor level and trajectories planned by the robot

5. Laser scans and odometry used for estimating the pose.
6. tf topics on the robot.

12. Safety procedures

Teams are responsible to describe safety procedures of the robots used during the challenge. A document describing such procedures and risk analysis must be submitted at registration time and will be used by the referee at any time to guarantee safety when using the robot and to instruct customers participating in the episode.

Appendix A Score Sheet Simulation Version

Team_____

Trial_____

Run_____

Execution time_____

Achievements:

- The robot correctly reports all the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers for all tables with customers.
- The robot reaches an unserved table and asks the order.
- The robot correctly understands (through speech) and communicates the order of the customer to the counter.
- The robot correctly recognizes the wrong or missing item and corrects the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.

Penalties:

- The robot hits any of the furniture or objects (one penalty for each hit).
- The robot requires multiple repetition of the speech command / The robot requires multiple repetition of a customer speech act.

Disqualifying behaviors:

- The robot hits a human.

Appendix B Score Sheet Remote Participation with Real Robot Version

Team_____

Trial_____

Run_____

Execution time_____

Achievements:

- The robot correctly reports all the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers for all tables with customers.
- The robot reaches an unserved table to take the order.
- The robot uses sign language to greet and ask for the order of a deaf-mute person
- The robot correctly understands and informs the order of a customer to the counter. (1 achievement when using speech. 2 achievements when sign language interpretation is used)
- The robot correctly recognizes the wrong or missing item and corrects the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.

Penalties:

- The robot hits any of the furniture or objects (one penalty for each hit).
- The robot requires multiple repetition of the speech command / The robot requires multiple repetition of the sign language from deaf person.

Disqualifying behaviors.

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot damages the furniture and/or objects.

SCIROC 2021

Episode 02: Sign language

Rulebook

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1. General Description

The concept of inclusivity is fundamental to modern society. For this reason, robotics and artificial intelligence must also take essential steps to make the services offered by the most modern technologies usable by the largest possible number of people. This goal implies the need for robots to provide their services also to people with special needs.

In the context of the Coffee Shop assistant robot proposed by the SciRoc 2021 (i.e., the second SciRoc) competition, an essential step towards the concept of inclusiveness is undoubtedly the possibility for the robot to understand and perform sign language (SL). On this basis, the idea of this second challenge was born, which will evaluate the robot's ability to effectively understand a customer who addresses it using sign language and can subsequently respond using the same language.

SL is a structured form of hand gestures involving visual motions and signs, which is used as a communication system. SL involves the use of different parts of the body (mostly fingers and hand expressions) to deliver information [1]. The second SciRoc challenge will be held in Bologna (Italy), the sign language used will be a subset of Italian language (LIS sign language). The signs taken into consideration are signs specifically designed to facilitate the interaction between consumers and barmen in the context of the Coffee Shop. Here is the list of signs (with the relative English translation) taken into consideration:

Execution phase for sign execution

Simple signs:

Caffe (Coffee)
Cocacola (Cocacola)
Euro (Eur)
Grazie (Thanks)
Limone* (Use video in “New signs” folder into Dataset) (Lemon)
The (Tea)
Cracker (Cracker)
Acqua (Water)
Bicchiere (Glass)
WC (WC)
Tovagliolo (Napkin)
Gomma da masticare (Chewing gum)
Birra alla spina (Draft beer)
Patate (Potatoes)
Bevande/bere (Drinks)
Cibo/mangiare (Foods)
Panino (Sandwich)

Composed signs

Buongiorno (Good morning)
Caffe macchiato (Coffee macchiato)
Succo di frutta (Fruit juice)
Acqua frizzante (Sparkling water)
Acqua da rubinetto (Tap water)
Vino rosso (Red wine)
Patate al forno (Baked potatoes)
Patate fritte (Fried potatoes)

Sentences

Buongiorno, desidera?* (Use video in “New signs” folder into Dataset) (Good morning, what would you like to order?)
Buongiorno, mi dica? (Good morning, please tell me)
Grazie, ciao (Thanks, bye)
Grazie, saluti (Thanks, greetings)
Latte caldo (Hot milk)
Latte freddo (Cold milk)
Caffe dopo (Coffee later)
Per favore, un caffè (Please, one coffee)
Sì, un euro (Yes, one eur)

Mi scusi, il conto da-darmi* (Use video in “New signs” folder into Dataset) (Excuse me, give me the bill)

WC uomini e a destra (men’s WC on the right)

Per favore, bicchiere uno (Please, one glass)

Caffe non c e mi dispiace (There is no coffee, I feel sorry)

Interpretation phase for sign recognition

Simple signs

Caffe (Coffee)

Cappuccino (Cappuccino)

Cocacola (Cocacola)

Euro (Eur)

Grazie (Thanks)

Limone* (Use video in “Initial signs” folder into Dataset) (Lemon)

The (Tea)

Cracker (Cracker)

Acqua (Water)

Gelato (Ice cream)

Bicchiere (Glass)

WC (WC)

Tovagliolo (Napkin)

Gomma da masticare (Chewing gum)

Birra alla spina (Draft beer)

Patate (Potatoes)

Bevande/bere (Drinks)

Cibo/mangiare (Foods)

Panino (Sandwich)

Composed signs

Buongiorno (Good morning)

Caffe macchiato (Coffee macchiato)

Succo di frutta (Fruit juice)

Acqua frizzante (Sparkling water)

Acqua da rubinetto (Tap water)

Vino rosso (Red wine)

Patate al forno (Baked potatoes)

Patate fritte (Fried potatoes)

Sentences

Buongiorno, desidera? * (Use video in “Initial signs” folder into Dataset) (Good morning, what would you like to order?)

Buongiorno, mi dica? (Good morning, please tell me)
Grazie, ciao (Thanks, bye)
Grazie, saluti (Thanks, greetings)
Latte caldo (Hot milk)
Latte freddo (Cold milk)
Caffe dopo (Coffee later)
Per favore, un caffè (Please, one coffee)
Sì, un euro (Yes, one eur)
Mi scusi, il conto da-darmi * (Use video in “Initial signs” folder into Dataset) (Excuse me, give me the bill)
WC uomini e a destra (Men’s WC on the right)
Per favore, bicchiere uno (Please, one glass)
Caffe non c e mi dispiace (There is no coffee, I feel sorry)

N.B: The names of the signs are identifiers, they must be communicated to the central controller following exactly the syntax expressed in this document.

2.Main scientific challenge

SL is a gesture based language for communication of deaf and dumb people. It is basically a non-verbal language which is usually used to deaf and dumb people to communicate more effectively with each other or normal people. SL contains special rules and grammar for expressing effectively. Basically there are two main sign language recognition approaches, image-based and sensor-based [2].

In SciRoc 2, **sign language recognition** approach is image-based, a technical challenge that encompasses multiple difficulties that the participating teams must overcome to achieve a satisfactory result. In the recognition phase, the robot must be able to recognize 2 simple signs and 1 composed sign effectively and be able to correctly trace the evolution of hand movements to extract the meaning of 1 sentence composed of several different signs performed by LIS experts.

Regarding **sign language execution**, the robot must be able to execute 1 simple sign, 1 composed sign and 1 sentence accordingly, making the process of interpretation by the human user immediate and straightforward. Moreover, the execution must be carried out in a well-balanced amount of time, which is neither too fast nor too slow, to ensure a simple and not frustrating experience for a possible user.

3. Platforms allowed

Any robot with an arm and a hand with five fingers can participate in the challenge. Thanks to the support provided by PAL Robotics, a TIAGo robot with one hand and one arm (see Fig.1) will be available to support both on-site and remote participants.

4. Scenario Setup

Two different scenarios are proposed, (1) a **sign recognition scenario** and (2) a **sign execution scenario**. In both scenarios there will be a central controller connected to a monitor to give both the robot and the human performers information about the signs to execute. The robot should be placed in front of the monitor, with its back to it, so that the cameras cannot in any way frame the information shown on the screen.

For the sign recognition scenario, the robot will be put in front of a human agent that will perform the signs to be recognized. The central controller will communicate to the performer the sign to execute through the monitor. The robot will communicate with the central controller sending the sign interpretation that will be displayed on the same monitor.

In the sign execution scenario, the robot will be put in front of three LIS experts, which will judge the robot's sign execution by filling out the questionnaire. The central controller will communicate to the robot the sign to execute and will display it on the monitor.

A TIAGo robot with one hand and one arm will be available to support both sign recognition scenario and sign execution scenario.

Figure 1: TIAGo Robot

5. Software configuration for participation with the TIAGo robot

A private gitlab repository will be created and shared with all the participants. The repository will contain a docker image provided by PAL robotics. The repository will also include the instructions related to downloading, running the docker and detailed documentation about the simulation environment and the TIAGo robot. A summary of the **topics, services, actions** and **APIs** useful for this challenge will be also provided in the repository. In order to start the docker loaded on this repository, users will need to log in the docker daemon on gitlab.com and then enter their GitLab user and password. For user convenience, some scripts will be published that simplify the launch of a docker with GPU acceleration. Following the steps properly, users will be able to run gazebo, rviz or other graphical applications from within the docker container. To have an idea of how participants will be able to use the development environment out of the box we created a public docker in the [wiki.ros\(section 2\)](#). Once the docker is running in the user machine, a single roslaunch command will be required to open the simulation and have access to all the **topics, services and actions** to fully interact with the TIAGo in simulation. Participants will need to configure by themselves the camera and microphone of their development pc in order to interact with the already provided ros packages from the docker.

6. Procedure

The challenge is divided into two different sections: **recognition section** and **execution section**. In the sign recognition section, the robot is placed in front of the monitor, a LIS expert will perform 2 simple signs, 1 composed sign and 1 sentence that will be displayed on the central monitor (signs and sentences are listed in the interpretation phase). In the sign execution section, the robot will be placed in front of three LIS experts. It will execute 1 simple sign, 1 composed sign and 1 sentence (signs and sentences are listed in the execution phase) that will be also displayed on the central monitor.

7. Timing

The maximum allowed time for a single trial of the sign recognition section is 15 minutes (+ 15 minutes of preparation). The maximum allowed time for a single trial of the sign execution section is 15minutes (+ 15 minutes of preparation). Note that the

effective trial execution time is an important element in this episode and faster solutions are considered to be better in case of ties in the number of achievements.

8. Score

Achievements of recognition section:

- Recognizing the first two simple signs (two points each)
- Recognizing the second sign (4 points)
- Recognizing the sentence (5 points)

Achievements of execution section:

- Executing the simple sign (2 points if above (\geq) 80 % of positive judge's perception (≥ 4) over Q1, Q2, Q3 and Q4)
- Executing the composed sign (4 points if above (\geq) 80 % of positive judge's perception (≥ 4) over Q5, Q6, Q7 and Q8.)
- Executing the sentence sign (5 points if above (\geq) 80 % of positive judge's perception (≥ 4) over Q9, Q10, Q11 and Q12.)

According to experts' advice, we designed the following questionnaire leveraging a 5-point Likert scale to evaluate the execution of signs generated by the robot.

	Absolutely yes (5)	Yes (4)	Neutral (3)	No (2)	Absolutely no (1)
(Q1) Have you understood the meaning of simple signs?					
(Q2) Are the shapes of simple signs correct?					
(Q3) Are the orientations of the palm of simple signs correct?					
(Q4) Are the movements of simple signs correct?					
(Q5) Have you understood the					

meaning of composed signs?					
(Q6) Are the shapes of composed signs correct?					
(Q7) Are the orientations of the palm of composed signs correct?					
(Q8) Are the movements of composed signs correct?					
(Q9) Have you understood the meaning of sentences?					
(Q10) Are the shapes of sentences correct?					
(Q11) Are the orientations of the palm of sentences correct?					
(Q12) Are the movements of sentences correct ?					

Overall score

The competition is executed in two independent sections of “sign recognition” and “sign execution” sections and an award is given for each section. Each section is arranged in two stages: 1) competition days, 2) final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the competition days qualify for the final to be held on the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the final. During the competition days, several runs will be available

to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the competition days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition Days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of scheduled episodes M, according to the following table:

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

The policy for tie braking will be:

- average of first n-1 highest scores
- average of next n-1 highest scores after the median (i.e. n-th highest score)

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same.

9. Ethical Issues

LIS experts involved in the episode, to act as customers, will be selected by the referees among team members, members of TC/OC, or deaf-mute people in advance.

The LIS experts will be invited to sign a consensus form where they declare to have been informed about the above mentioned information and that they volunteer to participate in the episode.

10. Detailed instructions for referees

The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule to ensure an equal access of the arena to the participating teams for the setup days. The referees must check the robots and approve their safety mechanism before the actual trials of the competition. Time

slots of 30 minutes (15 minutes of trial + 15 minutes of preparation and team exchange) is expected for every trial. Each team must be given an equal opportunity to perform multiple trials (minimum 3 to maximum 9 trials based on the time availability and the number of participating teams). For the sign recognition section, a referee and a LIS expert are required for the challenge execution. For the sign execution section, a referee and 3 LIS experts acting as interpreters are required for the challenge. The referees are expected to carefully study the rules and procedure of the benchmark before the competition. A consensus form must be given to LIS experts prior to the trial and the user evaluation form (i.e., questionnaire) has to be provided after the sign execution trial. For every trial, the referees must prepare the scenario according to the description provided in the "Procedures" section. To begin a trial, the referee must declare the starting of the challenge with a pre-determined visible signal. At the end of a trial the referees cross check the score with each other, record the execution time on the score sheet, and confirm the score with the team leader of the participating team.

9.1 GameController Instructions

For the management of the challenge, a central controller has two sections: interpretation section (for the sign recognition) and execution section. The controller has been implemented for the management of the different phases of the episodes' scenarios.

Upon opening the program, the following screen will appear:

In the IP field, enter the IP of the competing robot in the local subnet. The CheckBox is used to choose which of the two sections to start, the Interpretation section or the Execution section.

9.1.1 Interpretation section

The Interpretation section window will appear as follows:

By clicking on "send" the robot will be given the command to start interpreting, from that moment the robot will have one minute to interpret the sign performed by the human expert and send back the interpreted sign.

The result at the end of this operation will be the following

Clicking on “Next_sign” the system will advance to the next sign to recognize. At the end of the operation, the window will look like this:

9.1.2 Execution section

The window for the Execution section will appear as follows:

Clicking on “send” will trigger the sending of the set of signs that the robot has to execute. At the end of the procedure the window will look like this:

11. Detailed instructions for teams

Teams should communicate to the organizers in which of the sections (i.e., sign recognition, sign execution or both) they are willing to participate at least two weeks before the competition. Moreover, teams need to communicate to the organizers all the required information for operating the robot. During the competition, teams must prepare their robots outside the arena and can only enter the arena at the assigned times. They must follow the schedule of the trial and comply with the timings described in the "Timing" section. Once the referee signals the end of the trial, the participating team must immediately remove the robot from the arena to allow the next team to enter. Teams are kindly requested to log and store the robot's Internal data for every trial and to provide it to the organizers after the end of trials. This data will not be used during the competition, but it is used to produce and publish datasets for the benefit of the robotics community. This data must be expressed in the reference frame of the test bed which will be clearly marked on it. There are no restrictions about the framerate and data can be saved at the rate they are acquired or produced. Only data relevant to the episode is expected to be logged and can be in the format of rosbag, in particular the following data is expected to be logged:

1. Images processed for object perception and the calibration info for the images
2. point cloud used to recognize signs
3. The robot pose during signs executions

4. tf topics on the robot.

Communication with the central controller will be done via socket. The data needed to connect to the socket will be provided by the organizers during the setup days. The code for the central controller will be made publicly available before the beginning of the competition.

11. Safety procedures

Teams are responsible to describe safety procedures of the robots used during the challenge. A document describing such procedures and risk analysis must be submitted at registration time and will be used by the referee at any time to guarantee safety when using the robot and to instruct LIS experts participating in the episode.

Reference

[1] M. T. Cheek, Z. Omar and M. H. Jaward, "A review of hand gesture and sign language recognition techniques", *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, pp. 1-23, 2017.

[2] A. S. Nikam and A. G. Ambekar, "Sign language recognition using image based hand gesture recognition techniques," *2016 Online International Conference on Green Engineering and Technologies (IC-GET)*, 2016, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/GET.2016.79167

Appendix A Score Sheet Sign recognition section

Team_____

Trial_____

Run_____

Execution time_____

Achievements:

- Correctly recognizing the first simple sign (2 points).
- Correctly recognizing the second simple sign (2 points).
- Correctly recognizing the composed sign (4 points).
- Correctly recognizing the sentence (5 points).

Appendix B Score Sheet Sign execution section

Team_____

Trial_____

Run_____

Execution time_____

Achievements:

- Executing the simple sign (2 points if above (\geq) 80 % of positive judge's perception (≥ 4) over Q1, Q2, Q3 and Q4)
- Executing the composed sign (4 points if above (\geq) 80 % of positive judge's perception (≥ 4) over Q5, Q6, Q7 and Q8.)
- Executing the sentence sign (5 points if above (\geq) 80 % of positive judge's perception (≥ 4) over Q9, Q10, Q11 and Q12.)

SciRoc2021
Episode E03: Shopping Cart
Rulebook

Technical Committee

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1. General description

Episode E3 aims at evaluating the capability of a robot to interact with one challenging device found in environments designed for humans: the pushcart. Episode E3 is a joint effort between European projects [SciRoc](#) and [Eurobench](#), and it broadly corresponds to the BEAST (Benchmark-Enabling Active Shopping Trolley) Eurobench benchmark. Additional details about the characteristics and relevance of the scientific challenge tackled by Episode 3 are provided in [Section 2](#)

of this document, while limitations to the robots that can execute Episode 3 are described by [Section 4](#). An alternative version of Eurobench's BEAST benchmark involves a *walker* (i.e., a supporting wheeled device used by people experiencing difficulties in walking) instead of the cart; however, this version is not currently exploited by SciRoc.

The physical elements of the Episode compose its *testbed*. The BEAST testbed comprises two main elements:

- the *arena*, i.e. the passive structured environment where the Episode takes place;
- the *active shopping cart*, i.e. a robotized shopping cart capable of behaviors which include, but are not limited to, that of a standard cart.

More information about the testbed is provided by [Section 3](#) and [Section 6](#).

The aim of Episode E3 is to evaluate the capability of a mobile robot to correctly maneuver a wheeled device (shopping cart). In order to test the robot, it is assigned a path that it has to complete within a given time, while pushing the shopping cart. [Section 7](#) and [Section 8](#) provide additional information about the benchmarking protocol. In this context, “correctly maneuver” involves performance metrics concerning geometry (such as staying close to a predefined trajectory or maximising distance from obstacles), time, force (e.g., smooth application of force to the handle over time instead of abrupt bursts). [Section 9](#) describes the performance metrics.

The BEAST/Episode E3 benchmark makes use of the capability of the active element (cart or walker) of the testbed to simulate physical disturbances that occur in real-world scenarios, such as unevenly distributed wheel friction or small obstacles on the ground (such as a shallow step or a pebble).

Beside the physical version of the testbed, a simulated version is available. Additional information about it is provided in [Section 5](#) of this Rulebook.

2. Main Scientific Challenge

2.1 Pushcart Definition

A pushcart is a useful tool for humans in many scenarios and applications. The most common type of pushcart is the one used for grocery shopping, called *shopping cart* or *shopping trolley*. Humans are well educated in using a pushcart: in fact, its features and shape are designed to accommodate our physical embodiment. For these reasons, the use of a pushcart is not equally straightforward for robots. Hence, in order to provide a

clear and unambiguous definition of a pushcart employed in this episode we characterized a pushcart a device with the following features:

- The shopping cart is the only active element of the testbed.
- It is a wheeled mobile basket with a sensorized handle that allows it to register the force applied on it.
- The basket is mounted on a four wheeled chassis with fixed-axis front wheels¹.
- The fixed-axis front wheels are the only active wheels and they realise a differential drive kinematic structure.
- The rear wheels are passive pivoting wheels with negligible friction.
- The activation of the motors of the front-wheels generates a brake force that affects the rolling of the pushcart, following predefined patterns defined for each wheel.
- The activation of motors perturbate the behavior of the shopping cart when it is subjected to horizontal forces, in a controlled manner. Based on the type of the experiment carried on, the perturbation can be null, moderate or severe. It can be separately set for both wheels.
- The front wheels provide odometry data to estimate the angular and linear velocity of the robot with respect to the testbed origin reference frame.
- The zero of the active wheels is set before the beginning of the single test.
- On the front of the chassis, a laser scanner is fixed in order to provide the benchmarking system with information about the distance between the cart and the surrounding obstacles.
- The handle is similar to the one found on standard shopping carts. It is sensorized in order to track the forces applied by the robot to the handle.

[Section 5](#) and [Section 6](#) of this document provide information about the setup used to implement both the simulated and real pushcart in the context of Episode 3.

It must be noted that generally pushcarts do not have any active mechanisms influencing the dynamic behaviour of the cart. However, unintentional alterations to the pushcart behaviour are frequent. They are usually due to faults and/or obstructions, and include:

- friction, either constant or dependent on angular position;
- limitations on the angular range;
- torque opposing wheels rotation, either constant or dependent on the angular position;
- effect of other users operating the pushcart from different angles;

In real-world situations many events can influence a pushcart maneuvering task, thus leading to a wide range of altered pushcart motions with respect to the expected behavior. Episode 3, for the time being, focuses on

¹ Please note that this is not the only type of pushcart used as a shopping cart. Sometimes the fixed-axis wheels are the back ones, other times all four wheels can pivot.

basic pushcart behaviours. The authors of this document are well aware that most of the above alterations to pushcart behaviour can be simulated by introducing suitable actuation and control actions, and have already devised the technical means through which such alterations can be introduced. For this reason, the pushcart environment described in [Section 5](#) and [Section 6](#) is designed to support the installation of additional components aimed at this goal.

2.2 Challenges

Dexterous motions and gestures are of key interest to address countless applications where a robot has to act on the environment. This is especially relevant for humanoid robots that are designed to surrogate -- and eventually substitute -- human motions, and to properly behave in a human-friendly world. In fact, human environments, and their components, are designed to accommodate our bodies' shapes, strengths and limitations. For example let us consider the shape of keyboards, chairs, windows, doors and pushcarts. Operating in such environments without the capability to interact with those components is extremely difficult, and prevents agents from being effective and independent.

Robots are no exception, and to allow them to freely operate in our world, we need to provide them with the ability to smoothly interact with all the environmental components, and to replicate human motions. This is an extremely challenging task that has become to be regarded as fundamental to truly enable autonomy in robots.

In this episode, we focus on one of these robot-environment interactions to improve local robot behaviour in addressing pushcarts [Nikdel et al., 2018; Hirano, 2018; Arai et al., 2000]. In particular, this episode is designed to provide a common testbed and a baseline for generating effective behaviours for robots acting in typical human-populated environments. Since pushcarts, or variants of them, are a constant and dynamic component of our scenarios, being capable of mastering them is key to develop autonomy in robots. Moreover, not being able to cope with such everyday-life components can be harmful, as it might prevent the robot from completing its jobs in supporting humans.

The community has already shown a great interest in tackling such a problem. Given the existing literature, the task of pushing a cart (a trolley or in general a big movable object) can be divided in four distinct phases: (i) detection and object localization; (ii) grasping point computation; (iii) manipulation and navigation. Hence, related works can be classified in accordance to their contribution to these phases. For example, several approaches have been proposed to object detection. Similarly, [Eital et al., 2020; Hermans et al., 2012] provide a 3D object detection framework where they validate, through actual interaction, whether an object can be pushed and they adjust the generated 3D model in accordance with a robot push-trial. Conversely, by exploiting a different 3D object representation [Deng et al., 2020] introduce a self-supervised routine to augment the 3D object datasets and learn a model to infer (first in simulation and then in real settings) the 6D object pose for robot manipulation. Moreover, if we consider the problem of object detection out of the scope of manipulation and pushing, then we can investigate a plethora of contributions to the task of object detection and pose estimation. For example, the work in [Tremblay et al., 2018] and [Mitash et al., 2017] exploit deep learning in order to infer the 3D object position and 3D mesh respectively. Upon detection and pose estimation, in Episode 3, the robot is required to approach the pushcart. Several works contribute to the state-of-the-art in robot locomotion. Such phase is key to have an exploitable positioning of the robot with respect to the pushcart. Such a task is usually considered as a navigation and positioning task, which is not strictly depending on the object to approach [Kriegel et al., 2011; Koyuncu et al., 2010]. However, we can

summarize the key aspects that might affect a successful robot positioning in the object-target appearance, and the robot embodiment [Gomez et al., 2013].

Once the robot reaches the desired configuration nearby the pushcart, it can initiate the manipulation phase which is key to this episode and usually requires the robot to decide the manipulation contact points (robot end-effectors to pushcart handle), and perform the desired movement [Li et al., 2015]. This is a crucial phase of the task that requires visual monitoring and manipulation, simultaneously. For example, in a different application with a similar objective, [Rusu et al., 2009;Klingbeil et al., 2010] exploit 3D laser scan to detect the type of objects that can be grasped and determine robot motions. [Meeussen et al., 2010] improve handle detection by considering both geometry and appearance. Then, upon detection, the authors use a compliant and force controlled task formalism (TFF - Task Frame Formalism) to plan for robot motions. More closely related to Episode 3, the authors in [Yu et al., 2005] compute object's inertia parameters in order to determine the most suitable contact points and push an object along a desired trajectory. Conversely, the work in [Park et al., 2016] presents a framework for monitoring an object manipulation task during execution and, in case, correct an anomaly. In a different setting that can be easily transferred to the pushcart domain the authors in [Arai et al., 2000] present a framework for human-robot collaborative object-lifting tasks. Even if in Episode 3, there is no collaboration involved, it is important to mention also this category of approaches that share the same robotics control theory and implementation techniques. Finally, we point to the work in [Stüber et al., 2020] that provides an exhaustive overview of the most recent literature in robotics object-pushing tasks.

The last phase of the task is to push the pushcart along a desired trajectory, and can be initiated once the robot has reached the pushcart, estimated the contact points and successfully grasped it. Such a phase can be considered as the sum of two concurrent tasks: a manipulation task (as introduced before) and a navigation task. While the majority of approaches explore only the latter and provide effective solutions to a trajectory generation and locomotion problems [Ravankar et al., 2018; Mavrogiannis et al., 2019], a smaller set of approaches are closely related to the challenge proposed in Episode 3 and focus on object pushing and navigation. For example, the authors in [Nikdel et al., 2018; Hirano 2018] determine a pushcart trajectory in both a hands-free human following task [Nikdel et al., 2018], and pushcart maneuvering task [Hirano 2018]. Differently, in [Takeda et al., 2017] the authors present an approach for generating the best pose for a robot in an assistive scenario interacting with external forces. Finally, the authors of [Murooka et al., 2015] present a framework to enable humanoid robots to exploit their full kinematics to push big objects.

Despite the remarkable contributions and effort done to address and complete this challenge, proposed solutions still do not satisfy the expected level of dexterity nor achieve the desired natural and robust behaviour. This suggests the difficulty of mastering such a task for an autonomous robot, and the need to tackle such a challenge. In the SciRoc project we propose Episode 3 to contribute in this direction. The goal, in fact, is to define a standardised way to test the capabilities of autonomous robots to solve the pushcart (or in general movable objects) problems described in this section. In doing so, Episode 3 leverages the methodological framework developed by former research projects RoCKIn and RockEU2 [Amigoni et al., 2015]. In fact the ambition of Episode 3 is to go beyond a simple “pushcart test” and aim, instead, at a scientifically grounded “object pushing benchmark”.

3. Testbed

The testbed is composed of an arena and an active (i.e., robotized) cart, plus a few additional pieces of equipment for network and processing. Since the shopping cart is not designed to be disassembled, the only piece of the testbed that requires physical assembling is the arena.

The walls of the arena are composed of 1 m tall panels, and include two apertures. One of them goes down to the ground, and is used for entry and exit; the other is a cutout in the surrounding wall. The arena has 1m-tall walls, and includes four pillars, two set along one wall and two along the major axis. While executing the benchmark, the robot is expected to avoid any contact between these elements of the arena and any part of its body or of the cart. Structural support is provided to the arena by a rigid frame built from modular aluminium profiles. Below are images of the arena and of the active shopping cart.

The active shopping cart is based on a commercial product, modified to introduce sensing and actuation. Though significant, the modifications have been carefully designed and carried out to avoid interfering in the behavior and usability of the underlying device, so that the “active” nature of the resulting robotized machine only emerges when it is necessary to introduce disturbances. Concerning these, though the active components of the BEAST benchmark are fully capable of autonomous action, for safety reasons disturbances are kept limited to resistance to motion imposed by the user.

The active cart *never acts on its own*: it can only oppose, in a configurable way, to the actions of the robot (or person) operating them. No motion is ever initiated by the cart.

The active shopping cart is equipped with sensors that perceive both the surrounding environment (LiDAR) and the mechanical actions performed by the robot on the cart itself. The latter are measured via a modified cart handle, equipped with load cells (see image below left). The cells’ electrical signals are processed by custom electronics and made available to the cart’s ROS system. The actuation capabilities of the active cart rely on a differential-drive “drive unit” mounted in place of the cart’s front wheels (see image below right).

Further information about the construction of the arena is provided by [Section 6](#).

4. Platforms Allowed

The BEAST benchmark is suitable for any autonomous mobile agent that is physically capable of operating the active trolley in the arena. As such, it can be executed by any robot provided with an end-effector(s) suitable for interaction with the active cart's handle, including (but not limited to) humanoid robots. Execution of the benchmark by humans, while not explicitly considered, is nonetheless fully possible: thus making it possible to collect "human baseline" datasets to be compared with those generated by robots.

5. Simulated (Remote) Scenario Setup

In addition to its physical realization, the testbed for Episode 3 is also available in simulation. The simulated scenario setup is composed of a replica of the testbed arena where the Pal Robotics Reem-C robot starts placed right in front of the shopping cart and the shopping cart is in the zero position of the circuit. The chassis of the cart supports the basket and is placed on four wheels: two fixed-axis front wheels and two caster rear wheels. The fixed-axis front wheels are the only active wheels and they realise a differential drive kinematic structure. The rear wheels are passive pivoting wheels with no friction. From a sensory perspective, the shopping cart is equipped with a laser scanner and a force sensor on the handle. The laser scanner is a LiDAR and is used to carry out the measurement of the distance of the closer obstacle to the cart.

The force sensor is placed on the conjunction of the handle with the chassis. It measures all the contacts with the handle in force, direction and duration but, on the final topic, all the contacts are filtered and only the contact with the Reem-C and the cart are provided. The cart can be easily moved within the arena and several disturbance profiles can be set on the front wheels. As in the real robot (on-site) scenario, these disturbance profiles are specified by LUT files for each rotation degree of the wheels. The wheel rolling provides also the odometry measurement and this is used to provide linear and angular velocity of the shopping cart with respect to the arena origin reference frame.

The simulator runs in Ubuntu Linux and it is configured as a docker container. Such a setup makes the configuration and installation routine pretty straightforward, but on the other hand, introduces hard constraints on the hosting machine. The simulator can be installed, and it has been tested, on the following ubuntu versions: Ubuntu 16.04.7 LTS (Xenial Xerus); Ubuntu 18.04.5 LTS (Bionic Beaver); Ubuntu 20.04 LTS (Focal Fossa). The docker container extends the `osrf/ros:kinetic-desktop-full` docker (https://github.com/craymichael/ros-kinetic-nvidia-docker) that contains opengl, glvnd and cuda 8.0. This makes opengl work from any docker environment when used with `nvidia-docker2` (https://github.com/NVIDIA/nvidia-docker). Hence, the simulator can only run on a machine that features an NVIDIA graphic card that supports CUDA with the NVIDIA drivers installed.

The architecture of the simulated environment is developed within Gazebo and it is composed of a set of nodes that mimic the real-scenario setup. More in detail, the nodes are:

- Core node: controls the benchmark status and provides low level functionalities to evaluate it.
- Simulation-state collector: it is the bridge between the valuation system and Gazebo.
- The gazebo pushcart plugin updates the simulated pushcart parameters (Laser scans, handle contact force, wheel look up tables (LUT)).
- The Gazebo simulator.

Further details are provided in the simulator manual, which includes: (i) a description of the architecture; (ii) instructions on how to install the simulator; (iii) instructions on how to run a benchmark session. The manual can be found at the following link: https://github.com/madrob-beast/eurobench_benchmarking_simulation_software/blob/main/Beast_simulator_manual.pdf

The figure below shows a view of the simulated environment. A video showing the benchmark can be seen at <https://youtu.be/NeHachh8fAU>. The simulated environment is started with a preconfigured custom-made pushcart resembling the most common shopping-cart, and a Reem-C robot spawned next to it. As illustrated in the figure the arena respects the same size specifications described in [Section 3](#).

6. Real Robot (On-site) Scenario Setup

As explained in [Section 3](#), the scenario setup is composed of an arena and an active (i.e., robotized) shopping cart, plus a few additional pieces of equipment for network and processing. Setup is simplified and even if performed from scratch (with the arena broken down to its components) should not take more than a workday for an experienced operator.

Since the shopping cart is not designed to be disassembled, the only piece of the testbed that requires physical assembling is the arena. The walls of the arena are composed of 1 m tall panels; considering that the panels are supported by aluminium profiles which are themselves supported by adjustable feet, the actual height of the top of the walls from the ground is approximately 107 cm.

The arena includes two apertures. One of them goes down to the ground, and is used for entry and exit; the other is a cutout in the surrounding wall. The orange pillars that are part of the arena are heavy PVC tubes for construction (wall thickness ~4 mm), while the white panels composing the walls of the arena are made of low-density PVC, similar to the commercial product called Forex (5 mm thickness; 4 mm for the curved walls).

Structural support is provided to the arena by a rigid frame built from modular aluminium profiles with a 40 x 40 mm square cross section. Profile elements sport an 8 mm wide groove, used both to insert mechanical joints (e.g, those used to connect profiles, described below) and to guide and contain the edge of the wall elements, as shown in the picture on the right.

The aluminium profiles composing the arena are interconnected by robust 90° joints (80 by 80 mm) that constrain the geometry of the whole structure. The image on the right shows two of such joints.

In order to accommodate possible unevenness of the floor along the (quite extensive) perimeter of the arena, the whole structure is supported by adjustable feet. Below are images of the arena and of the active shopping

cart, as shown by the picture on the right. Due to the adjustable feet, the height of the elements of the arena from the ground is not predetermined, and can range approximately from 30 mm to 50 mm.

7. Procedure

While executing the benchmark, the shopping cart (pushed by the robot) has to follow the trajectory shown in the image on the right. Such trajectory is composed of four parts:

1. a first part where the cart should proceed along a straight line parallel to the longer walls of the arena;
2. a second part where the cart is required to invert its direction of motion by going around a pillar (no specifications are given on trajectory shape here: however, if planning is not done correctly -considering the differential drive kinematics of the front wheels of the trolley- the execution of this part of the benchmark can easily lead to collisions and/or require backtracking);
3. a third part that requires that the cart passes between the same couple of pillars where the first section began, but in the opposite direction (no constraints are imposed to trajectory shape, except that the cart must pass between the pillars without touching them);
4. a fourth section where the cart needs to be “parked” in the corner of the testbed.

More specifically, the phases of the protocol of Episode 3 are defined with respect to the numbered Checkpoints (line segments) in the image above. Such phases are:

1. The trolley is positioned in the start pose, where the central point between its front wheels (i.e., the actuated ones) is in the center of Checkpoint 4. This phase is human-executed and not part of the benchmark. The robot is positioned inside the area of the testbed, between the trolley and the entrance to the testbed, in front of the center point of the trolley's handle, at a sufficient distance from it that in order to reach the handle the robot has to move its whole body with respect to the ground. The referees are in charge of defining such distance.
2. The benchmark is started.
3. The robot has to grasp the trolley's handle. The robot can optionally start with its end effectors already positioned on the handle. In that case this step is human-executed before the start of the benchmark (step 2).
4. The robot has to navigate, while pushing the trolley, through all checkpoints in the correct order (from 1 to 5). During navigation, neither the robot nor the trolley must touch any element of the arena (walls or pillars)
5. The benchmark reaches its end. The conditions that cause the benchmark to end are specified in [Section 9](#).

8. Timing

Each execution of Episode 3 by a robot is called a **run** of the benchmark. The final score achieved by each team depends on its performance over multiple runs of the benchmark, according to the scoring mechanism defined by the European Robotics League (of which SciRoc is part).

Runs occur according to a schedule prepared by the referees. Scheduled times for the runs of a given team are published by the referees in advance of the runs. Such times are not flexible. In particular, the scheduled

end time for each run is rigidly enforced² and is not influenced by the fact that the robot is, or is not, ready at the scheduled start time. These times are defined as follows:

- **Scheduled start time** is defined as the time chosen by the referees for the beginning of the run;
- **Scheduled end time** is defined as scheduled start time + timeout.

In case of delays due to the organisation, the scheduled start time is moved forward accordingly in order not to penalise the teams.

The start of a run occurs at the scheduled start time if the robot is ready to execute the benchmark. If it is not ready:

- if the robot gets ready after the scheduled start time but before the scheduled end time for the run, the run starts as soon as the robot is ready;
- if the robot gets ready after the scheduled end time for the run, the run does not take place at all.

The end of a run occurs when the scheduled end time is reached. The run ends earlier if any of the following events occur:

1. the robot enacts a disqualifying behaviour (see [Section 9](#));
2. a team member makes a request to the referees to stop the Episode.

The execution time used for the scoring (see [Section 9](#)) is always the actual duration of the run, i.e. from actual start time to actual end time. Values of the execution time are always between zero and the maximum timeout for Episode 3. The maximum value of the execution time is only available to robots that are ready at the scheduled start time.

The following table recapitulates when the start and end of a run of Episode 3 occur:

The run starts...	The run ends...
between scheduled start time and scheduled end time, as soon as robot is ready	as soon as any of the following occurs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● scheduled end time reached ● a disqualifying behaviour occurs ● team requests to stop the Episode

For organisational reasons, scheduled times for the runs can be changed by the referees and republished after their first publication. When this occurs, the referees make sure that the teams involved by the changes are aware of them and, if possible, get feedback from the teams before finalising the changes.

² This rigidity is necessary to preserve the timing of the SciRoc Challenge, in order to make it more attractive to the public. Unexpected pauses and delays have, in fact, a heavily disruptive effect on an event such as the Challenge and must be avoided. Also, rigidity in timing ensures that the scoring takes into consideration the capability of a team to get the robot ready for a benchmark in a reliable and repeatable way.

8.1 Timeout

For Episode 3, timeout has a predefined maximum value, called maximum timeout. Maximum timeout for Episode 3 is **10 minutes**. The timeout value used while managing benchmark runs is a percentage of the maximum timeout, increasing monotonically during the course of the benchmark according to the following mechanism:

- timeout is 50% of maximum timeout until the robot reaches the **achievement threshold** defined in [Section 9](#);
- timeout increases to 100% of the maximum timeout as soon as the robot reaches the achievement threshold.

This variable timeout mechanism aims at preserving the interest of the public by ending early the benchmark runs where the robot is stuck, inactive or ineffective.

9. Score

The scoring mechanism for this Episode complies with the framework used by the European Robotics League for Task Benchmarks and specified in the [ERL Consumer Rulebook](#). It is based on the three sets of Achievements, Penalising Behaviors and Disqualifying Behaviors described in the following Sections.

9.1 Achievements

The list of the Achievements of Episode 3 is the following:

A1 - The robot has autonomously grasped the trolley's handle, without any human intervention. This Achievement cannot be collected if the benchmark has been started with the robot's end effectors already on the cart's handle.

A2 - The trolley has reached Checkpoint 1. The trajectory of the trolley during this part of the benchmark should be as close to parallel to the side wall as possible. Assessment of deviations does not affect the Achievements, but will be used to break ties.

A3 - The trolley has reached Checkpoint 2.

A4 - The trolley has reached Checkpoint 3.

A5 - The trolley has reached Checkpoint 4.

A6 - The trolley has reached Checkpoint 5.

Checkpoints are defined in [Section 7](#).

Achievements can be collected only in the specified order. In order to collect Achievement A_k , the robot must have already achieved Achievements $A_1 \dots A_{k-1}$, with the only exception of A_1 in case the benchmark has been started with the robot's end effectors already on the cart's handle.

Achievement A2 is the **achievement threshold** for Episode 3.

Achievements A2...A6 require that the trolley, pushed by the robot, reaches specific checkpoints. The definition of “Reaching a checkpoint” is the following:

- The trolley **reaches a checkpoint** when the projection on the floor of the central point between its two front wheels (i.e., the actuated wheels) crosses the line segment corresponding to the checkpoint.

Let CP be the checkpoint that an Achievement is associated to. If the trolley reaches any checkpoint different from CP before it reaches CP, the benchmark gets interrupted by the referees and no further Achievements can be collected. When the execution of the benchmark gets interrupted in this way, the duration of its execution is conventionally set to the full allowed duration up to the timeout (this is done to avoid unfair advantage to robots that provoke an interruption, since execution time is used to break ties).

For Achievements A2...A6 no constraints are imposed to trajectory shape beyond those imposed by the definition of “reaching a checkpoint”.

9.2 Penalising Behaviors

The list of the Penalising Behaviors of Episode 3 is the following:

PB1 - The robot or the cart hits any piece of the benchmark setup without inflicting damage. An exception is made for the elements of the shopping cart, which can be hit by the robot without penalty (provided that they do not get damaged).

PB2 - The robot falls down and requires that the robot’s team performs a manual get-up.

For the definition of the Penalising Behaviors (and, later, of the Disqualifying Behaviors) the following definitions of “damage” and “hit” are used:

- A **damage** is any geometric change that does not revert spontaneously within 10 seconds, even if the change would be reversible through suitable intervention (e.g., a wall panel is pushed out of its normal position).
- A **hit** is a physical contact event where the robot applies forces sufficient to cause damage (even if no damage occurs): referees are in charge of deciding what physical contacts must be classified as hits.

An additional penalising behaviour is inflicted to the team every time the corresponding event occurs, even if the team has already been penalised for the very same behavior.

9.3 Disqualifying Behaviors

The list of the Disqualifying Behaviors of Episode 3 is the following:

DB1 - The robot hits a human (e.g., a referee).

DB2 - The robot damages any piece of the benchmark setup.

DB3 - The robot exits the testbed area³.

DB4 - The trolley moves for a duration of 5 s or more while the robot is continuously in contact with any part of it different from the handle, **OR** the overall time that the trolley moves while the robot is in contact with any part of it different from the handle is over 30 s.

9.4 Ties

It may happen that two robots get the exact same number of Achievements and the exact same number of Penalising Behaviors, without incurring into any Disqualifying Behaviors. In this case, to avoid ties, the following criterium is applied⁴:

tie-breaking criterium: the performance of the robot which finished the benchmark in a shorter time is considered as better.

10. Requirements for the organizers

The elements of the Episode are self-contained and do not require specific preparation and/or infrastructure from the organizers of the Competition.

The most challenging request made by the Episode concerns the physical space required to install the arena. The arena itself has a rectangular envelope on the ground of 3 m by 6 m, but requires additional space during its setup to allow for easy manipulation and assemblage of its components.

When set up, the benchmark only needs -beyond the space occupied by the arena- some space around it to let the referees observe the execution of the benchmark, plus an area free of obstacles in front of the aperture that participating robots use to enter and exit the arena.

For what concerns networking, the testbed already includes the equipment needed to cater for its necessities. The only remaining infrastructural need is the availability of a 230 VAC / 300 W power outlet.

11. Instructions for the Referees

The information included in [Section 7](#) (Procedure), [Section 8](#) (Timing) and [Section 9](#) (Score) should be sufficient to inform referees about -respectively- the events expected during the execution of the benchmark of Episode 3, and the aspects of such events that are significant with respect to the robot's score.

³ The robot is considered as outside the testbed area when none of its elements has a projection on the floor that lies inside the 3 m by 6 m rectangular area of the floor which contains the testbed.

⁴ Additional performance metrics that may (but not necessarily will) be used to break ties that cannot be broken with the tie-breaking criterium are the following:

Time To Grip Handle: time from start of the benchmark to first contact of the robot with the trolley handle.

Time To Checkpoint n: time from the instant the trolley starts to move to the instant the trolley crosses checkpoint N.

Roughness of Actuation: maximum force applied to the handle of the trolley.

Safety of Navigation: minimum distance of the trolley from obstacles.

Capability Level: number of steps of the benchmark protocol actually completed by the robot.

12. Instructions for the Teams

The information included in [Section 7](#) (Procedure) , [Section 8](#) (Timing) and [Section 9](#) (Score) should be sufficient to inform teams about -respectively- what their robot and themselves are expected to do during the execution of the benchmark of Episode 3, what elements of such execution have an impact on their robot's score, and what is such impact.

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SciRoc 2021
Episode 04: Delivery of Emergency Medicines
Rulebook

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1. General Description

A medicine is ordered by a person in Bologna that cannot go out (due to quarantine-related issues or because the person is disabled). The robot must be able to move autonomously to the location where the citizen is waiting. The robot might need to detect and avoid possible obstacles on the way (static and dynamic), and it must consider that GPS coverage is not always guaranteed. Once the robot arrives at the citizen location, the robot should interact with him/her (in English) to deliver the proper medicine. Depending on the person's health, it could be also possible that the robot should accompany the person to the nearest medical centre to see a doctor.

2. Main scientific challenge

This episode aims at benchmarking some of the key functionalities required by an autonomous ground robot to operate in dynamic and challenging environments, such as localization, trajectory planning, and obstacle detection and avoidance. A secondary functionality, while being basic for the episode success, is the ability to interact with people through language (English).

A survey in social aware navigation can be seen in [5]. A human aware mobile motion planner and anticipative kinodynamic robot planner are explained in [6] and [9]. Prediction of human motion intentionality is described in [10]. Guiding people in a shopping mall and in an airport can be seen in [12] and [4]. Side-by-side accompanying people is explained in [1], [2], [3] and [8]. Accompanying a group of people is described in [7], [4] and [13]. Robots approaching a person can be seen in [11].

This episode wishes to push advanced developments in the context of Smart Cities and last-centimeter delivery, focusing on autonomous capabilities and navigation for ground robots, as these are important milestones to achieve for the emergency robotic systems of the future.

3. Platforms allowed

Ground robots that can navigate in outdoor (and maybe indoor spaces), detect and avoid obstacles (dynamic and static), and have incorporated basic human-robot interaction with the citizen.

The ground robots must have a system to carry and deliver items to specific locations (see [Section 4](#) for details).

Specific limitations may be applied to large ground robots for safety reasons (maximum 60cm length, 60cm width and 160cm tall). Apart from this, any ground robot platform will be able to enter the competition for this episode.

The robot has to have an emergency switch button and optionally a Lidar or a bumper for avoiding collisions with close objects or persons.

4. Scenario Setup

The episode must take place in an urban area of Bologna. A minimum ground floor area of 10x10 m² is expected for this episode.

A specific point inside the arena must be defined as the **medical centre** as the starting point for ground robots, ideally close to one of the entry points to the arena. This position on the ground will be the origin of the coordinate system of the arena, i.e. origin=(X=0, Y=0, Z=0). This position must be marked on the floor with some kind of visible marker (e.g. stickers).

A second specific point in the arena must be defined as the **citizen area** to which robots need to arrive. This position will be measured in meters from the start position, i.e. customer=(X=TBD, Y=TBD, Z=0). This position can be marked on the floor with some kind of visible marker (e.g. stickers). Around this marker, in a maximum radius of around 4m, there can be at most 2 people, where only one is the target.

The medicine can be represented approximately by a box of 15cm x 10cm x 10cm.

A small area for the team's **control station** must be set next to the medical centre location. There must be an entry point to the arena nearby, so it is directly accessible for team members. The control station must have electric power for laptops and battery chargers, and two tables with a minimum size of 2x1 m. Each table must be equipped with at least 4 chairs and 1 monitor (with power and HDMI cables).

Also, fixed (and mobile) **obstacles** could be included within this area. Depending on the specific area, dead ends and indoor spaces could be used to incorporate more realism into the episode.

Two main considerations for all the obstacles:

- The visual appearance of the obstacles should NOT be homogeneous (flat color), otherwise vision-based approaches will most likely fail.
- The minimum size of the obstacles in any dimension should be 20cm, to make sure onboard sensors can detect them (i.e. avoid the use of light poles).

As soon as a list of items to be used as obstacles is found by the local organizers, and agreed with the technical committee of this episode, the detailed descriptions with pictures of the obstacles should be provided to the participating teams.

There can be two different obstacle dispositions, so teams face the delivery task with increasing difficulty:

- Easy: use fixed obstacles between the medical centre and the citizen location.
- Hard: use fixed and mobile obstacles between the medical centre and the citizen location.

The disposition of obstacles in the arena must enable the navigation of the ground robots between the start and the customer location, in terms of available free space and safety separation from such obstacles (at least 1 meter).

After offering the arena to teams for practicing during the first one or two days, we propose to organize the execution of the episode in two rounds of time slots (for each difficulty level),

each one taking place on a different competition day. The idea is that teams are accumulating achievements during all three rounds, so the best team is the one that achieves the most difficult task (see score sheet for more details). During the Final, the team will only face the Hard configuration of the obstacle, potentially with new unseen obstacles or a reduced available time to complete the objective.

Regarding the **variability** of the scenario, the medical centre and citizen locations may change depending on the difficulty level and the number of participants. Between runs, the obstacle configuration may change up to 2 meters, so we prevent teams to build the solution during practice using map-based or teach & replay approaches.

5. Bologna Data Hub Interaction

TBC.

6. Procedure

This section describes the step-by-step procedure for a complete run of the episode. A single run consists of two phases that are executed sequentially without any interruptions. A robot can automatically continue to the next phase at any time if it is unable to execute or fully complete a phase. According to the episode description, the procedure is split into two phases.

Preparations and start

1. A medicine request reaches a pharmacy in downtown Bologna with the location of a person in need.
2. The responsible of the pharmacy attaches the medicine to the ground robot.
3. The run begins, and the time starts, with the medical manager placing the medicine on the ground robot.

Phase 1: Delivery of the medicine

1. The ground robot autonomously goes with the medicine towards the citizen location.
2. During the navigation, the robot may need to detect and avoid different obstacles (including pedestrians). There will be an increasing level of difficulty in the types and number of obstacles that the robot can encounter.
3. Once at the citizen area location, the robot has to find the target person by approaching the present people nearby.
 - a. Approaching should try to be face to face, meaning the robot should approach from the front (angle around 180°)
 - b. Once the robot is in front of the person, it should ask if it is the person in need of help (target person)
 - c. In case it is not, it should try with the next person in the area.
 - d. In case it is, it should deliver the medicine and continue with phase 2.
4. The interaction with a person can be done through a screen or with voice recognition.

Phase 2: Accompany to the medical centre

1. In case the person does not feel well and it is not enough with the medicine, the robot should ask the citizen to accompany him/her to the nearest medical centre.
2. Then, the robot will accompany the citizen until they arrive at the medical centre, overcoming dynamic (pedestrians or other robots) and static obstacles on the way. There will be an increasing level of difficulty in the types and number of obstacles that the robot can encounter.
 - a. Accompaniment should be side by side (90° of the motion direction) when in a wide area, otherwise, the robot should move ahead or behind the person to pass through narrow spaces.
 - b. The distance between the robot and the target person shouldn't be higher than 1.5m to be considered as close accompaniment.

7. Timing

The challenge will run on 3 days: 2 days for preliminaries (safety checks and robots compliance, and also for teams practice in the arena), and one day of finals.

Team participation can be organized in time slots of about 15 minutes. The start time will follow a fixed, and pre-defined time schedule (no delays for any reason). The referees will also inform the participating team 10 minutes before the start of the time slot to place their robots and equipment in one of the tables of the control station area, just outside the arena. They must leave the other table free for the next participating team.

After the time slot of 15 minutes finishes, the referees will inform that the next participating team has 10 minutes to place their robots and equipment in the free table of the control station, while the team that has just participated has the same 10 minutes to pick up all their things. In this way, the organizers' time schedule can be set as **blocks of 25 minutes** (10 minutes of preparation + 15 minutes of competition). Depending on how many teams finally participate, these numbers can be subject to modifications.

Teams will be able to attempt the delivery as many times as they wish within the time slot, always starting from the medical centre location. Take into account that the team score will not be the best attempt during the time slot, but an average of their top attempts (see [Section 8](#)). The time taken between the start and end of the run will also be recorded, as faster solutions are considered to be better in case of ties in the number of achievements.

It is a good idea to show on a big screen a time **countdown** of the time slot, so it is clear for all teams and also for the audience.

8. Score

The scoring mechanism used for this episode is the same one used for the Task Benchmarks of the European Robotics League. As such, it is based on three sets: Achievements, Penalising behaviours and Disqualifying behaviours. Apart from these sets, the whole time of

the operation will be recorded, to break ties between teams with the same amount of achievements.

Achievements

1. Reaching the citizen area location avoiding obstacles.
2. Reaching the citizen area location within the first 2 minutes after the time slot starts.
3. Approaching at least one citizen.
4. Approaching at least one citizen face to face.
5. Interacting with both citizens to confirm their identity.
6. Interaction done with voice recognition.
7. The medicine is delivered within the first 5 minutes after the time slot starts.
8. Accompanying the person side-by-side and adapting position in narrow areas (see [section 6](#)).
9. Accompanying the person staying close to the target person (see [section 6](#)).
10. Reaching the medical centre accompanying the person.
11. Reaching the medical centre accompanying the person in 8 minutes after the time slot starts.
12. Transmitting live information (images/video, robot position, etc) to the control station.

Penalising behaviours

1. Manual interventions to the ground robot in case it needs to be recovered from a failure (more details in [Section 10](#)).
2. Hitting any of the structures in the arena (obstacles...).

Disqualifying behaviours

1. The robot hits the citizen.
2. The robot damages the structures in the arena (obstacles, safety net...).

8.1 Admission to the ranking

Each (scheduled) execution of the episode by a robot is called a **run** of the benchmark. The final score achieved by the robot depends on its performance over multiple runs of the benchmark.

In order to be admitted to the ranking, a robot must have performed **at least 3 successful runs** of the benchmark.

A *successful* run is one where the robot collected at least one achievement.

8.2 Overall score

The competition is arranged in two stages: 1) Competition Days, 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held on the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the Final. During the competition days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team,

it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the Competition days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition days will be determined according to the scoring system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of episodes scheduled M, according to the following table

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of a tie score for access to the Final, the policy for tie-breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

Tiebreaker: In the case in which two teams have the same score, the minimum execution time over all the runs of the teams will break ties.

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same. If teams with the same score are in the border limit to access the Final, all such teams will enter the Final.

9. Detailed instructions for referees

There must be two referees for evaluating this episode. The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule to ensure equal access of the arena to the participating teams for the setup and competition days.

BEFORE THE EPISODE

Safety checks

During the setup days, all robots will be checked by the referees for compliance. Only robots that successfully pass the safety checks will be able to participate in the competition.

Referees will check the safety mechanism of all the robots that intend to participate, which must be communicated by each team. If the robot has other mechanical devices (e.g. a manipulator), their safety must be demonstrated as well.

Scenario setup

Referees must place obstacles in the arena according to the level of difficulty of the time slot.

Before each time slot, referees must determine the medical centre and citizen locations. Referees must communicate to the participating team that they can start moving their robots and equipment to one of the tables of the control station 10 minutes prior to the time slot start.

After these 10 minutes, referees must take a medicine to be delivered, and hand it to the team for attaching it to the robot. At this point, referees can announce the start of the time slot and start the countdown of 15 minutes.

DURING THE EPISODE

Between runs within a time slot, the obstacles should be moved up to 2m around their current location to prevent teams from using training-based approaches.

Referees must take notes of all achievements and penalising behaviours using a score sheet per time slot. One of the referees, Referee 1, will be in charge of filling the score sheet and will stay at the control station with other team members. The other referee, Referee 2, must be able to move throughout the arena close to the robot, will check the robot performance and other achievements, and will have a timer to record the time of each run. Ideally, both referees should have a direct communication link via walkie-talkie or similar.

Referee 1 will check the live transmission of data at the ground station, among other achievements. Special attention must be put when scoring the obstacle detection and avoidance. Teams must show Referee 1 an online proof that obstacles are being autonomously detected and avoided, for example explaining and showing the control station screen using the received images, highlighting the obstacle and/or the robot trajectory.

Referee 2 will check if the robot is running in autonomous or manual mode, will also check the proximity of the robot when it reaches the citizen location, as well as the actual interaction and delivery, and will also check if the robot hits any obstacles.

Manual interventions incurring in penalising behaviours are defined as physically interacting with the robot in order to continue the runs, for example due to: hitting any obstacles, malfunction if it does not respond to manual control, etc. Any manipulation of the robot is allowed without penalisation only if it is done in the starting medical centre location.

AFTER THE EPISODE

Referees must announce the end of the time slot, and let the following participating team 10 minutes to set up on the second table at the control station, while the current team also has these 10 minutes to pick up all their equipment.

Both referees must check the results of the participating team on the score sheet, and after agreement they must sign it. Then, they must show the results to the team leader in case there is any misunderstanding, and the team leader must sign it as well once discrepancies have been clarified, if any.

10. Detailed instructions for teams

BEFORE THE EPISODE

Safety checks

Teams may use different robots during different time slots. Teams must inform the referees of all robots that they intend to use, and each robot must pass a safety check before being used. Only robots that successfully pass the safety checks will be able to participate in the competition.

If the robot has other mechanical devices (e.g. a manipulator), their safety must be demonstrated as well.

This check can be done at any time during the setup days. When teams are ready for an inspection, they can request one from the referees.

Scenario setup

A medicine to be delivered will be provided by the referees at the medical centre location. Teams have 10 minutes to set up in one of the tables of the control station, and must wait outside the arena for the start of their time slot. Teams may power up their equipment during the setup time, including the robot.

DURING THE EPISODE

The referees will indicate the start of the time slot. Then, the team is allowed to enter the arena. They can attach the medicine to the ground robot using whatever mechanism they have designed for the competition.

There will be one referee next to the control station, and another one next to the ground robot. Team members at the control station must clearly show if the obstacles are being detected and avoided in an autonomous manner, for example explaining and showing the control station screen using the received images, highlighting the obstacle and/or the aerial robot trajectory.

Manual interventions incurring in penalising behaviours are defined as physically interacting with the robot in order to continue the runs, for example due to: hitting any obstacles, malfunction if it does not respond to manual control, etc. Any manipulation of the robot is allowed without penalisation only if it is done in the starting medical centre location.

AFTER THE EPISODE

At the end of the time slot, the team leader will receive the score sheet from the referees in order to check the team performance, and after solving any discrepancy, he/she must sign it.

11. Ethical issues

Volunteers involved in the episode, to act as citizens, will be selected by the referees among team members, members of the technical/organizing committees, or adult citizens. In case of using real citizens they will be informed about the episode, its procedure, how to interact with the robot for communicating the order and about the safety procedures.

The citizens will be invited to sign a consensus form where they declare to have been informed about the above mentioned information and that they volunteer to participate in the episode.

12. Safety procedures

The only safety procedures concerning the setup of this episode concern the physical confinement of the arena. The area should be closed to external people that are not related to the competition.

Concerning the execution of this episode, there should always be someone carrying the remote emergency switch button, and paying attention to the robot behavior in order to stop its movement on any risk observed.

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Appendix A. Score sheet

Team Name: _____ Difficulty level (Easy/Hard): _____

Run Number: _____ Execution Time: _____

Referee 1: _____ Referee 2: _____

Achievements:

- Reaching the citizen area location avoiding obstacles.
- Reaching the citizen area location within the first 2 minutes after the time slot starts.
- Approaching at least one citizen.
- Approaching at least one citizen face to face.
- Interacting with both citizens to confirm their identity.
- Interaction done with voice recognition.
- The medicine is delivered within the first 5 minutes after the time slot starts.
- Accompanying the person side-by-side and adapting position in narrow areas.
- Accompanying the person staying close to the target person
- Reaching the medical centre accompanying the person.
- Reaching the medical centre accompanying the person in 8 minutes after the time slot starts.
- Transmitting live information (images/video, robot position, etc) to the control station.

Penalising behaviours:

- The robot hits any of the structures in the arena. Number of hits: _____
- The robot needs manual intervention during a run.

Disqualifying behaviours:

- The robot hits the customer.
- The robot hits and damages structures in the arena.

Notes:

Referee 1 signature	Referee 2 signature	Team leader signature

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Appendix B. Team information sheet

Not applicable.

SciRoc 2021

Episode 05: Shopping Pick & Pack

Rulebook

Technical Committee

Daniele Nardi, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

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1. General Description

This episode addresses the problem of picking products from a storage container and placing them on a designated shelf. The chosen domain is the operation of an autonomous shop, where the robot helps to manage the inventory of a shop and to organise newly arrived products.

2. Main Scientific Challenges

The main functionality tested in this episode is *mobile manipulation* using an autonomous robot. In the latest years, mobile manipulation has become a problem of interest among researchers due to the variety and complexity of challenges and robot capabilities that are involved. For instance, in a grocery store setting, there are so many complexities that a robotic hand or gripper should take into account, such as handling objects of different weight, sizes, shapes, texture and compliance. Picking up a bag of pet food is very different from picking up bananas or cucumbers.

Different robotic competitions [1-6] have picking and packing problem, aiming at 1) measuring the performance of these complex systems, 2) defining metrics and assessing benchmarking criteria, 3) fostering research and development of new approaches and technologies, and 4) creating awareness and drawing more attention from the general public to robotics.

For example, in the educational ICRA DJI RoboMaster Mobile Manipulation Challenge [1] teams of students were challenged either to design and develop a self-made lightweight mobile manipulator or to use a standard robot that could autonomously pick, transport, and stack fixed-sized building blocks. The RoCKIn@Work competition [2] defined a more challenging task by increasing the complexity of tasks and a variety of objects to manipulate. In particular, teams were required to develop robots autonomously switching between tasks and capable of performing mobile manipulation for assembly processes, quality control, order handling, and logistics. The main objective of the competition consisted in pushing teams to develop new solutions to perception, motion planning and grasping. With respect to other competitions, RoCKIn adopted a sophisticated approach with multifaceted scoring of both tasks and functionalities. However, all tasks were predefined - without orders coming at

execution time - and for each object a CAD model was provided. A similar approach has been recently transferred to RoboCup@Work [4]. Conversely, the Amazon Picking Challenge [5] introduced work orders that were specified offline just prior to each run, while adopting a simple scoring system. The challenge consisted in designing an autonomous robot to pick items from warehouse shelves, with objects belonging to 25 known categories of different sizes. The adopted gripper revealed to be a key factor for succeeding in the competition. Finally, the EuRoC Floor Logistics and Manipulation challenge [6] assessed mobile manipulation capabilities both in simulation and remote robot control. From each of the aforementioned competitions, a large variety of diverse solutions at a hardware, software and algorithmic level originated [5, 7, 8]. These solutions are now becoming the starting point for teams participating in new editions of the competitions.

In the SciRoc competitions, we adopt a systematic evaluation approach with a scoring system similar to RoCKIn [2]. In the first edition of the SciRoc in 2019, this Episode was focusing on picking individual items from shop shelves and placing them in a container to compose customer order. The items were of different size and shape and should not have been damaged during transportation. Moreover, the benchmarking approach, developed by Ocado for EU project SoMa [9], is used as a reference to evaluate the performance of grasping.

Thus, this SciRoc episode “Shopping: Pick and Pack” challenge contributes in benchmarking mobile manipulation abilities of robots also focusing on a realistic business scenario. In this competition, the challenge includes picking grocery items from a storage container and organising items on designated shelves.

3. Platforms allowed

Tasks must be completed using a fully autonomous robotic platform with mobile manipulation and perception capabilities (e.g., KUKA YouBot, Tiago, etc.). In particular, the robot must be able to navigate autonomously in the environment to reach the products inside a storage container or to place items on a shelf. In addition, the robot must be able to detect, grasp and manipulate products in order to deliver them to the designated location. Moreover, the robot should be easily moved in and out of the competition zone, even when not in function, by maximum two team members with minimum effort.

The robot must have a noticeable **emergency stop button** that can be pressed at any time by any people involved in the episode (referees, users, team members, etc.) to shut off all motors in case of emergency. Teams must provide a document describing safety procedures and risk analysis for the use of their robot and any other equipment used during the challenge (see Section 12).

Robot inspection will be performed to test safety devices and procedures before the runs of the competition. No robot is allowed to participate in any test if safety procedures are not completed. Teams have to guarantee that safety devices and procedures are always working and enabled. Referees can check safety procedures at any time during the competition.

4. Scenario Setup

The episode takes place in an area reproducing a grocery shop. The shop is built with a picking area with a storage container and shelves where products need to be placed.

Figure 1. Scenario layout.

The total area of the episode will be approximately eight by eight meters, as shown in Fig. 1. The scenario includes:

- A preparation area delimited with safety separators and a safety door that is reserved for the team that is about to start the next episode. Within this area any action on the robot is allowed and no score can be gained. As soon as a robot exits the preparation area, it cannot re-enter it. The robot has to autonomously exit the preparation area. The team has to clear this area as soon as possible, while the robot is performing the trial and the area can be occupied by the next team to start setup for the next run.
- A start/finish area (2 x 1.5 m) delimited with markers on the ground. In every test, the robot starts from this area.
- A storage container (External dimensions: 600 x 400 x 205 mm; Internal dimensions: 378 x 272 x 147 mm) is placed at a fixed location with all the products that need to be placed on the shelf.
- Two shelving units (see example at the bottom of the document) labelled with a unique identification number. Among the available shelves, products will have designated locations that are arranged at different heights that are suitable for small-sized robots (e.g., YouBot) and for big-sized robots (e.g., Tiago). Within the same shelf, products might be placed at different levels.

Common grocery items will be used as objects for pick and place task. The detailed description of all furniture and grocery items will be provided to the participating teams according to the schedule given in Section 6.2.

5. Procedure

The episode will include one container that will be placed on a fixed location. The Container will contain all the objects that need to be stacked on the shelf.

Storage container: the container will have, K number of products that can have different types, packaging size and that needs to be placed at different shelf levels. Shelf level and packaging size of the products will be decided by the referees and will be the same for all teams during the same trial. The number K of products is fixed for all teams during the same day. Each product is assigned a level of difficulty: easy, medium or hard. In particular, teams face the delivery task with increasing difficulty that will take place in different competition days:

- Qualification round 1 - the order requires two products of easy level of difficulty (K=2).
- Qualification round 2 - the order requires four products of easy and medium levels of difficulty (K=4).
- Final - six products of medium and hard levels of difficulty; including one duplicate and one new product from round 2 (K=6).

Clutter: The objects in the container will be placed with different levels of clutter:

- Ordered - all products are separated from each other with no contact and are placed in particular orientation (Qualification round 1);
- Ordered random - same product category are together but in random orientation with contact (Qualification round 2);
- Random - randomly placed inside the container (Final).

Delivered product: a product is considered as delivered only when it is placed on the designated shelf without being in contact with any part of the robot, and the robot has announced its delivery.

Runs/trials: a single run or trial consists of P *steps* (a single phase repeating P times) executed sequentially without any interruptions and in any order, starting from the start area. Once it is left, the start area cannot be re-entered. During a single step, the robot can only deliver **one of the K products** to the designated shelf. A robot can automatically continue to the next step at any time if it is unable to execute or fully complete a step, provided this transition is announced. The robot must announce the start of a new step (pick of a new product) to allow the referee and the audience better understand the behaviour of the robot. Similarly, the robot must announce the delivery of each of the products as well as the end of the trial once entered in the finish area. When the robot announces the end of the trial from the finish area the products are delivered by the human operator to the customer. To stop the time, the robot must simultaneously be in the finish area and announce the end of the trial. Hence, if the robot does not announce the end of the trial, the time is not stopped even if the robot is located in the finish area.

5.1 Expected behaviour of the robot

Preparations and start of the trial

- The robot is positioned in the starting area.
- A referee places all the objects in the container.
- The trial begins at the scheduled time; the timer starts..
- When ready, the robot leaves the start area. The start area must be left by the robot within the first 5 minutes from the episode start.

Single step

- The robot approaches the container.
- The robot perceives the container and chooses a product to deliver and announces it.
- The robot perceives and grasps the announced product.
- The robot delivers the product to the designated shelf, leaving it there. The product is considered delivered according to the definition provided at the beginning of this section.
- The robot announces the delivery of the product.

Multiple steps and finish of the trial

- After the execution of a single step, a new step can be started or the robot can go to the finish area and announce the end of the trial.
- After the robot announces the end of the trial while being in the finish area, the products are delivered by the human operator.

5.2 Team information and schedule

Any information (e.g., shelving, product details, communication protocol for the hub, etc.) will be provided to the teams 4-5 weeks before the competition.

The scenario in which the episode will run will be available during the setup days. Any mapping procedure can be performed, no major changes will be applied during the competition.

6. Timing

The maximum allowed time for a single qualification trial is **20** minutes. The timer starts immediately after the customer order is sent. During this time slot the team may attempt only one run of the episode.

The run for each team will start strictly at the scheduled time in order to avoid time shifts. Teams that are not ready to start at the designated time will lose some time but will still be able to run their test until the end of the assigned time slot. If a robot cannot start the episode (i.e., leave the start area) within the first 5 minutes of the time slot, it will be asked to be moved

away. Time stops either at expiration or when the robot moves to the finish area and announces that it has completed the trial. Note that time is an important factor in this episode, and faster solutions are considered better in case of ties in the number of achievements.

In any case, the start area must be cleared within the first 5 minutes of the slot assigned to each team. After the robot exits the start area, teams have to clear the area immediately removing any other equipment (laptops, power cords, etc.). Further on, the start area becomes a finish position.

7. Score

The score of the episode is determined as a sum of points defined in a set of achievements and penalisations, based on objective measures.

7.1 Achievements

- The robot announces the start of a new step.
- The robot grasps a product (independently of its type). (Repeatable)
- The robot delivers a correct product to the robot delivery area. (Repeatable)
- The robot correctly places as per orientation of other products on the shelf (Repeatable)
- The order delivers all the K products.
- Data Hub updated correctly for the remaining products on shelves. (Repeatable)
- The robot reaches the finish area.

7.2 Penalising behaviours

- The robot hits any of the furniture and objects. (Repeatable)
- The robot drops an object. (Repeatable)
- The robot announces the completion of a step when the product is not yet fully delivered. (Repeatable)
- The robot announces the delivery of an item which is not in the order or which has been already delivered. (Repeatable)
- The robot enters the finish area but does not announce the end of the trial within one minute.

7.3 Disqualifying behaviours

The episode is immediately stopped and any score achieved will be cancelled.

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot hits and damages the furniture and/or objects.

7.4 Overall score

The competition is arranged in two stages: 1) Competition Days (qualification rounds), 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held in the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the Final. During the competition days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the Competition days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of episodes scheduled M , according to the following table

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the Final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

Tie breaker: In the case in which two teams have the same score the cumulative execution time over all the runs of the teams will break ties.

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same. If teams with the same score are in the border limit to access the Final, all such teams will enter the Final.

8. Detailed instructions for referees

The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule to ensure an equal access of the arena to the participating teams for the setup days. Also they must make sure that all products in the shop are provided to the teams during the setup days for training purposes. The referees must check the robots and approve their safety mechanism before the actual trials of the competition.

Once the arena has been built, and before allowing the teams to access the arena, the referees must mark the start and finish locations, products and other furniture to ensure they are placed back on their default locations for the trials.

A competition schedule for the competition trials must be prepared in advance. Time slots of 30 minutes (20 minute trials + 10 minutes of preparation and team exchange) is expected for every qualification trial. Each team must be given an equal opportunity to perform multiple trials (minimum 3 to maximum 9 per day, based on the time availability and the number of participating teams).

A minimum number of 2 referees are required for execution of the test. The referees should try to initialize the scenario before the trial and assign roles to the customer to collect orders.

For every trial, the referees must prepare the scenario according to the description provided in the “Procedures” section by distributing products in the shelves according to the schema available in the digital hub. In particular, they must establish the shelf level and packaging size of the products to deliver, and they must collect an order of K products according to the difficulty level of the day. The difficulty of different trials should be comparable.

To begin a trial, one of the referees must be standing at the order handout desk. They have the responsibility of announcing the start and stop of the benchmark according to the schedule. Referees are also in charge of) keeping track of the time and 3) placing and removing the objects from the storage container and designated placement shelves.. The second referee will always be in the human operator’s area, ensuring the safe operation of the robot at all times and scoring the achievements and penalties using the provided score sheets.

At the end of a trial the referees cross check the score with each other, record the execution time on the score sheet, and confirm the score with the team leader of the participating team.

9. Detailed instructions for teams

Teams need to show safety mechanisms of their robots and to demonstrate their use once before the competition begins. They also need to communicate to the organizers the required information for operating and stopping the robot.

During the competition, teams must prepare their robots outside the arena and can only enter the arena at the assigned times. They must follow the schedule of the trial and comply with the timings described in the “Timing” section. Once the referee signals the end of the trial, the participating team must immediately remove the robot from the arena to allow the next team to enter. In particular, the robot can start the episode (i.e., leave the start area) at any time, but the time of the episode is fixed in the schedule and does not depend on the robot actions. If the robot is not able to leave the start area within the first 5 minutes of the time slot available to the team, the team will have to give up the run and clear the start area immediately. The test finishes at the scheduled time (i.e., 15 minutes after the scheduled start). When the episode ends, team have to remove the robot from the arena within 2 minutes, exiting through the finish area.

Teams are kindly requested to log and store the robot’s Internal data for every trial and to provide it to the organizers after the end of trials. This data will not be used during the competition, but it is used to produce and publish datasets for the benefit of the robotics

community. This data must be expressed in the reference frame of the test bed which will be clearly marked on it. There are no restrictions about the framerate and data can be saved at the rate they are acquired or produced. Only data relevant to the episode is expected to be logged and can be in the format of *rosvbag*, in particular the following data is expected to be logged:

1. Images processed for object perception and the calibration info for the images.
2. Point clouds used to recognize an object.
3. 2D estimated robot poses and 2D trajectories planned by the robot.
4. Laser scans and odometry used for estimating the pose.
5. Static transforms among robot frames.
6. Arm and gripper trajectories planned by the robot.

10. Ethical issues

Customers involved in the episode will be selected by referees among adult customers in the MK shopping mall. These customers will be informed about the task under execution.

The customers will be invited to sign a consensus form where they declare to have been informed about the above-mentioned information and that they volunteer to participate in the episode.

11. Safety procedures

The only humans inside the scenario are the referees. A specific safety separator will be provided by the constructors of the scenario to separate the robot movement and manipulation area from the human operator area.

Teams are responsible to describe safety procedures of the robots used during the challenge. A document describing such procedures and risk analysis must be submitted at registration time and will be used by referee at any time to guarantee safety when using the robot and to instruct customers participating to the episode.

12. Contingency plan for remote competition

In case of conducting the tournament in remote setup, the shelf used for placing the objects will be replaced with additional storage containers. The episode will be modified to pick from one container and place in another container as per the category.

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Appendix A. Score sheet

Team: _____

Execution Time: _____

Trial number: _____

Achievements:

- The robot announces the start of a new step.
- The robot grasps a product (independently of its type). No. ____
- The robot delivers a correct product to the robot delivery area. No. ____
- The order delivers all the K products.
- Data Hub updated correctly for the remaining products on shelves. No. ____
- The robot reaches the finish area.

Penalizing behaviors:

- The robot hits any of the furniture and objects. No. ____
- The robot drops an object. No. ____
- The robot delivers a product which is not in the order. No. ____
- The robot does not announce the end of the trial while in the finish area.

Disqualifying behaviors:

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot damages objects and furniture

Notes:

Appendix B. Reference image for shelves

Appendix C. Reference image of container

Appendix D. Reference image of objects